

D8.3

Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Strategy 2nd version

Project name

Deployment and Assessment of Predictive modelling, environmentally sustainable and emerging digital technologies and tools for improving the resilience of IWW against Climate change and other extremes

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	Name	Organisation	Date
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1.0	29/02/2024	DBC	Final submitted version

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
DCES	Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Strategy
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
ER	Exploitable Result
KER	Key Exploitable Result
ROI	Return of Investment
TBD	To Be Defined
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package
IWW	Inland waterway
IWT	Inland waterway market
KPI	Key Performance Indicator

Executive Summary

The current document presents the PLOTTO dissemination, communication and exploitation plans, which detail the activities to be conducted throughout the course of the project to achieve maximum visibility and enhance its impact within the research community. A strategy is created, which identifies the appropriate targets of the dissemination effort, as well as the communications channels and tools to be used, leading to the formulation of a complete dissemination and communication plan. Similarly, the opportunities for exploitation are explored, analysing exploitable items and joint exploitation prospects to timely create a robust understanding of the project's output potential. Key insights regarding the Inland Waterway (IWW) market are presented. In addition, a standardization and liaison plan identifying bodies and communities related to the project's interests is included, further increasing its overall potential. The plans are accompanied by monitoring mechanisms, which ensure the viability and tractability of the overall dissemination and exploitation plan.

1 Introduction

1.1 Project information

The project entitled “**Deployment and assessment of predictive modelling, environmentally sustainable and emerging digital technologies and tools for improving the resilience of IWW against climate change and other extremes (PLOTOTO)**” aims at increasing the resilience of the IWW and the connected hinterland infrastructures, especially under adverse conditions, such as extreme weather, accidents and other kinds of hazards. In doing this, downscaled climate change scenarios will be combined with simulation tools and actual data, to provide operators an integrated tool able to support more effective management of their infrastructures at strategic and operational levels.

PLOTOTO project consists in the deployment and assessment of predictive modelling, environmentally sustainable and emerging digital technologies and tools for improving the resilience of IWW against climate change and other extremes. An integrated tool is set up to allow relevant authorities to improve the efficiency of their infrastructures management. This tool is a combination of downscaled climate change scenarios with simulation tools and actual data. Six complementary avenues will be considered to achieve this integrated tool that will support relevant authorities and their operators for more effective management:

- Measure and use high-resolution modelling data for the determination and assessment of the climatic risk of the selected transport infrastructures and associated expected damages.
- Use existing data from various sources with new types of sensor-generated data (computer vision) to feed the used simulator.
- Utilise tailored weather forecasts (combining seamlessly all available data sources) for specific hot spots, providing real-time early warnings with corresponding impact assessment.
- Develop improved multi-temporal, multi-sensor UAV- and satellite-based observations with robust spectral analysis, computer vision and machine learning-based assessment for diverse transport infrastructures.
- Design and implement an integrated resilience assessment platform environment as an innovative planning tool that will permit a quantitative resilience assessment through an end-to-end simulation environment, running “what-if” impact/risk/resilience assessment scenarios. The effects of adaptation measures can be investigated by changing the hazard, exposure and vulnerability input parameters.
- Design and implement a Common Operational Picture (COP), including an enhanced visualisation interface and an Incident Management System (IMS).

The PLOTOTO integrated platform and its tools will be validated in three case studies in Belgium, Romania and Hungary.

1.2 Purpose of the deliverable

The purpose of deliverable D8.3 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Strategy 2nd version is to present a complete communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy, considering the intended audience, stakeholders, dissemination channels, appropriate communication tools, exploitation opportunities and standardization bodies.

This document is complementary to PLOTO deliverable D8.1 “Project Website, Corporate identity and general templates for dissemination material”. D8.1 presents the corporate design developed for the project, including the logo and style guidelines for all project promotional materials, document templates and the project website. It describes the brand rationale and lays out graphic identity guidelines for the correct use of the logo, brand colors, and typography by the PLOTO consortium.

This document also represents the revised edition of D8.2, titled "Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation Strategy 1st version," which was initially submitted in February 2023. The primary objective of this latest iteration is to enhance the communication and dissemination tools outlined in the preceding document.

1.3 Intended audience

This is a public document. For the consortium partners, this document serves as a guide for the use of the available PLOTO’s communications and dissemination tools, as well as related procedures to be respected. Also, it will be used to assess PLOTO’s potential regarding its commercial and marketing development. For interested stakeholders outside of the consortium, it helps to create an understanding of the project’s dissemination, communication, and exploitation strategy.

1.4 Structure of deliverable and relationship with other work packages/deliverables

The rest of the document is structured as follows:

- **Section 2** reiterates the objectives of the Communication strategy and the available tools to support it. It also presents the major changes impacting the communication strategy that will be influencing the communication targets.
- **Section 3** re-emphasises the PLOTO dissemination plan, dissemination opportunities, as well as dissemination Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).
- **Sections 4 - 8** describe the exploitation plan of the PLOTO project, providing a Key Exploitable Results analysis, the individual exploitation plans of the consortium partners, as well as describing the IPR Management, roadmap to market & business modelling methodology and preliminary findings from the initial market analysis and initial competition landscape analysis.
- **Section 9** describes the PLOTO standardization and liaison plan.
- **Section 10** provides some concluding remarks.

1.5 Main updates to previous version

The current version of the deliverable maintains the structure of the previous version (D8.2) while enriching its content with new information and additional insights. In particular, the following changes have been identified:

- ER list updated with two additional results
- Finalisation of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) selection
- Updates / adjustments in the Communication and Dissemination plans
- Inland waterway transport market insights
- Additional competitive landscape insights
- BMC, SWOT and PESTLE analyses for the project and per KER

2 Communication plan

2.1 Objectives

In the previous version of the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation strategy (D8.2), WP8 has crafted a comprehensive list of communication tools to support PLOTTO's external outreach. The strategy highlighted in it prioritised effective communication tools to raise awareness among stakeholders about the project's purpose, objectives, activities, and outcomes. This initial communication effort served as the cornerstone for fostering active engagement among stakeholders, establishing a collaborative environment.

In this updated version of D8.2, the strategy remarks again the key role of communication in promoting stakeholder involvement throughout the various stages of the project's development. It also outlines the planned communication activities for the upcoming months.

2.2 Communication channels and tools

As outlined in D8.1, the official PLOTTO logo has been shared with the consortium partners for effective internal and external communication regarding the project. This graphical element has been integrated with the EU-funding acknowledgement, along with instructions on its proper usage in project-related communications. Both graphical elements can be easily accessed and downloaded from the project's website's library. Additionally, the branding guidelines, available in the same repository, highlight techniques for accurately representing the project in communications.

The communications channels available to partners are:

- **Website:** the [webpages](#)' overall structure remains the one presented in D8.1 and it displays information about the project in a transparent and accessible manner and it comprises:
 - Homepage
 - Objectives
 - Pilot sites
 - Library
 - News & Events
 - Contact
- **LinkedIn:** The [PLOTTO page](#) serves as the primary social media platform for disseminating news and updates regarding the project and its consortium members. This online hub remains the key tool through which the professional community engages with the project and its associated EU affairs. As a standard practice, to bolster the ongoing growth of LinkedIn followers, posts will be shared on the PLOTTO page based on the available content, aiming for a frequency of 1-2 posts per week.
- **X:** This [account](#) provides support for both the website and LinkedIn platforms. The Consortium is aware of the existence of the project hashtag, #PLOTTO, which is to be used mandatorily whenever possible.
- **YouTube:** The PLOTTO account serves as a repository for video materials produced or to be created by the consortium as part of endeavours to enhance awareness about the project.
- **Newsletter:** The bi-annual newsletter compiles the most recent updates from the project and the consortium. It features a concise introduction outlining the highlights of the preceding 6

months of the project. Subsequently, two sections are dedicated to presenting the latest news available on the webpage and detailing upcoming events.

2.3 Main changes from the previous version

In the past year, most of the targeted values have been achieved. However, variations in current digital trends are affecting the use of some of the social media platforms listed above so the Key Performance Indicators should be revised.

In particular:

- X (formerly Twitter) has recently experienced a decline in prominence within the social media landscape, leading to a reduced interest in joining this platform. Consequently, the target value outlined in the table below (Table 1) should be substantially reassessed considering these evolving trends. The recommendation is to set a new target of reaching a total of 250 followers by the project's conclusion.
- It is important to regard YouTube solely as a repository tool rather than an interactive social media platform. In alignment with this perspective, the focus shifts from attaining a specific number of subscribers to a new benchmark – the quantity of videos uploaded on the dedicated channel. This benchmark is set at a total of 18 videos for the entire duration of the initiative.
- TV spots are not an effective means of increasing awareness about the project. Given the intricate technical details and developments associated with PLOTO, the general community exhibits limited interest. Consequently, the creation of the suggested TV spots is deemed a highly improbable option and the target should be reduced to zero.

Table 1: Revised KPI table

KPI	Description	Target	Status in M18	New targets
Project identity	Logo, branding guidelines, templates	1	1	
PLOTO general presentations	General presentations for key stakeholders (short and long version)	2	2	
Banners	Roll-up banner to present in general terms the project and more in details the pilot sites	2	2	
Posters	Poster to present the project	2	2	
Brochures	A4 brochure and 3-fold flyer, developed at project's start, updated in M18	1	1	
	Number of brochures distributed (per year)	200	150	
Newsletter	Project newsletter issued by-annually (per year)	2	2	
Videos	Promo videos presenting PLOTO solution and its components	2	To be planned	
	Number of views per video	1000		/
Website	Number of unique visitors (per year)	1000	1111	
	Number of views	250	3638	
News items	Articles online (per year)	≥ 12	53	
Press releases	Press releases (per year)	1	1	
X	Number of followers (per year)	+100	118	250
LinkedIn	Number of followers (per year)	+200	329	

YouTube	Number of subscribers (per year) Number of videos uploaded	+100	7	18
TV spots	Spots in TV (M24-M36-M42)	3		

3 Dissemination plan

3.1 Objectives, approval procedures, timing and reporting of dissemination activities

As highlighted in D8.2, PLOTO’s dissemination activities target various stakeholder groups, including among others regional/national water authorities, ministries of transport, freight companies, passenger organisations and associations, etc.

PLOTO consortium members planning to participate in events or dissemination activities for project representation must first secure approval from the Project Coordinator and Dissemination Manager, following the guidelines established in the previous document D8.2. Consortium members executing dissemination activities are required to record details in the internal PLOTO Dissemination Activities file (Figure 1).

Generally, inform the project’s Coordinator and the Dissemination manager 30 days before any dissemination activity. Objections, if any, must be submitted in writing within 20 days of receiving the notice. If no objections are received within this timeframe, the publication is considered approved, as detailed in the previous deliverable.

Journal publications, Technical & research papers, Conference proceedings, etc.									
No	Publication Title	Authors	Project Partners involved	Title of journal / magazine	Publisher	Publication date	Place of publication	Status	DOI/ available electronically at Archived
	(article title)	(authors name)	(organisation)	(title)	(publisher info)	(Publication date)		(Submitted / Published)	(Digital Object Identifier if applicable/ website link if available)
1									
2									

Figure 1: Dissemination Activities Record

3.2 Dissemination activities and tools

Open Access

In accordance with Article 17 of the PLOTO Grant Agreement, PLOTO partners are ensuring open access for all peer-reviewed scientific publications related to project results. These outcomes are already accessible on Zenodo, a repository supported by the European Commission and OpenAIRE. The Open AIRE profile for the project has been established and can be accessed through this link: https://explore.openaire.eu/search/project?projectId=corda_he::8526cb4c68e786ca6249c337dc30cf0e.

Deliverables

The deliverables due before January 2023 have been successfully submitted to the European Commission portal. Table 2 presents the upcoming ones.

Table 2: Revised list of deliverables

#	Deliverable Title	WP #	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination level	Due date
D1.3	Data Management Plan version 2	WP1	5 – DBC	R – Document, report	PU – Public	42
D3.3	Report on the dynamical downscaling of climate and atmospheric impacts final version	WP3	15 – FMI	R – Document, report	PU – Public	24
D3.4	Report on Dynamic Data Assimilation methodology and site-specific risk parameters and stressor indicators	WP3	18 – AUTH	R – Document, report	PU – Public	28
D4.4	Multi-Hazard Vulnerability Modules for IWW and connected hinterland infrastructures final version	WP4	12 – NTUA	OTHER	PU – Public	24
D4.5	Impact Assessment Model and Overall Organisational Resilience	WP4	16 – SoReCC	R – Document, report	PU – Public	34
D5.1	Assessment along the IWW corridor and a surrounding disaster affected area, using multi-source remote sensing data	WP5	12 – NTUA	R – Document, report	PU – Public	24
D5.2	Dynamic link to hazard and resilience assessment	WP5	16 – SoReCC	R – Document, report	PU – Public	30
D6.3	Business Continuity Models, Adaptation Strategies Standard Response Procedures	WP6	16 – SoReCC	R – Document, report	PU – Public	30
D7.1	The PLOTO Integrated System and Acceptance tests 1 st version	WP7	1 – INTRA	DEM – Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	PU – Public	32
D7.2	The PLOTO Integrated System and Acceptance tests final version	WP7	1 – INTRA	DEM – Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	PU – Public	38
D7.3	Reports on pilot testing, assessment and recommendations, plus training report 1 st version	WP7	1 – INTRA	R – Document, report	PU – Public	35
D7.4	Reports on pilot testing, assessment and recommendations, plus training report final version	WP7	1 – INTRA	R – Document, report	PU – Public	42

D8.4	Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Strategy final version	WP8	5 – DBC	R – Document, report	PU – Public	42
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Scientific Publications

To achieve the objectives specified in D8.2 regarding the dissemination of project outcomes, methodologies, or studies, it is essential to underscore that the non-exhaustive list encompassing specialized press, scientific journals, conferences, and other related activities remains a valid means of verification (Table 3 and Table 4). Importantly, it should be noted that these dissemination targets continue to be relevant in this update as well.

Table 3: Indicative list of scientific journals

Title	Acronym	Link	Relevant WP	Type
Science of the Total Environment	Sci. Total Environ.	Link	WP4, WP6	Hybrid
Structure and Infrastructure Engineering	Struct. Infrastruct. Eng.	Link	WP4, WP6	Hybrid
Reliability Engineering & System Safety	Reliab. Eng. Syst.	Link	WP4, WP6	Hybrid
Building Research & Information	Build. Res. Inf.	Link	WP4, WP6	Hybrid
Physics of Fluids	Phys. Fluids	Link	WP2, WP3	Hybrid
Meteorological Applications	Meteorol. Appl.	Link	WP2, WP3	Open access
Atmosphere	Atmosphere	Link	WP2, WP3	Open access
Journal of Flood Risk Management	J. Flood Risk Manag.	Link	WP4	Hybrid
Water Resources Management	Water Resour. Manag.	Link	WP4	Hybrid
Earthquake Engineering and Structural Dynamics	EESD	Link	WP4, WP6	Hybrid
Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering	BEE	Link	WP4, WP6	Hybrid
International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction	IJDRR	Link	WP4, WP6	Hybrid
Engineering Structures	EngStr	Link	WP4, WP6	Hybrid
Earthquake Spectra	EqSpectra	Link	WP4, WP6	Hybrid
Journal of Infrastructure Systems	JIS	Link	WP4, WP6, WP7	Hybrid
Environment Development and Sustainability	Environ. Dev. Sustain.	Link	WP3, WP5, WP4	Open access (APC)
Transportation Research Part E - Logistics and Transportation Review	TRANSPORT RES E-LOG	Link	WP3, WP5, WP4	Hybrid
Water	Water	Link	WP3, WP5, WP4	Open access
Applied Sciences	applsc	Link	WP4, WP5	Open access
Inventions	Inventions	Link	WP5, WP6	Open access
Sustainability	Sustainability	Link	WP2, WP3	Open access
Sustainable Transport Using Inland Waterways	Sustainable Transport Using Inland Waterways	Link	WP2, WP3	Open access

Table 4: List of scientific conferences, and other related activities

Title	Acronym	Place	Link	Relevant WP	Type
Connecting Europe Days	CED 2024	Brussels, Belgium	https://transport.ec.europa.eu/connectingeuropedays_en	All WP	In-person
Transport Research Arena 2024	TRA 2024	Dublin, Ireland	https://traconference.eu/	All WP	In-person
EUCNC 6G & Summit	EUCNC 6G Summit	Antwerp, Belgium	https://www.eucnc.eu/	All WP	In-person
ITS World Congress 2024	ITS WC 2024	Dubai, UAE	https://itsworldcongress.com/	All WP	In-person
World Conference for Earthquake Engineering	WCEE2024	Milan, Italy	https://www.wcee2024.it/	All WP	In-person

3.3 Dissemination Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The dissemination targets highlighted in D8.2 remain valid in this updated version, without any specific change. In Table 5, the targeted KPIs and the current values in month 18 of the project can be seen. The progress of the KPIs will be continuously monitored and, if necessary, edited in the future WP8 deliverable D8.4 “Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Strategy final version”).

Table 5: Dissemination KPIs:

KPI	Description	Target	Status M18
Project contacts	Stakeholder database (per year)	≥1.000	4870
Publicise Data	Entries in Horizon Results Platform (per year)	≥1	0
	Entries in Open AIRE (per year)	≥1	5
Scientific publications	Publications in open scientific journals/ conferences, Open Research Europe or book chapters (1-M12, 3-M24, 3-M36, 3-M42)	10	9
International Events & Conference	Participation in international events and conferences (per year)	≥ 2	3
Training sessions	Series of training opportunities on the pilot sites that will test the PLOTO AI-based tools (M24, M36)	≥3	To be planned
Workshops	Workshops (physical or virtual) with ≥ 100 Participants (M12, 24, M36)	≥3	1
Clustering with other projects	Joint Clustering Meetings (per year)	1	1
	Joint White paper (per year)	1	To be planned
	Joint Virtual Public Events (per year)	1	To be planned
Consensus workshop	Final Conference (physical or virtual) targeting ≥ 250 participants with key representatives (M42)	1	n/a

4 Exploitation plan

In this section, the exploitation plan for the entire project is presented, as well as the individual exploitation plans of the consortium partners for the individual Key Exploitable Results (KERs) of the project. Given that PLOTO is an on-going project, the development of the exploitation plan is a dynamic process, building on previous versions (D8.2) and evolving to accommodate any new aspects of the project. Moreover, emphasis is placed on the Key Exploitable Results, which are analyzed and updated accordingly.

PLOTO solutions aim at **increasing the resilience of IWW** enhancing via **multi-hazard risk understanding**, data integration and simulation modelling that allows for smart prevention and preparedness, as well as faster, adapted, and efficient response. The **new integrated system** supports **operational and strategic adaptation and mitigation measures**, by allowing for an absorption and **efficient recovery from climate change and disaster impacts**. The strong industrial and SME presence as well as the academic partners, research and end-user organisations involved with the PLOTO consortium will ensure that commercialization and exploitation activities are maintained and further intensified after the end of the project. To that end, the technology under development within PLOTO is expected to be exploitable and transformable into to **cost-effective, high-value products**. Exploitation activities will last for the entire project duration and will provide significant input for the system design and development. This iterative process between exploitation and development activities will allow for a fine-tuning of the proposed solutions according to current market needs and ensure that any new trends are taken into consideration. The initial exploitation plan for PLOTO, presented in the previous version of the deliverable, was based on the following cycle (Figure 2):

Figure 2: Exploitation process

Opportunity: Identification of the market opportunities for PLOTO by specifying the unmet customer needs that could be satisfied by the solutions developed through the project

Appraisal: Evaluation of the timing and other circumstances with a potential to affect the exploitation of the identified opportunities.

Solution: Fine-tuning of developed technologies to serve the unmet needs of customers or outperform competitors already covering those needs.

Commercialization: Evaluation of the profitability and market prospects of the developed solution.

Exploitation: Specification of the exploitation activities that will best place the developed solution in the market and maximise its profitability.

Furthermore, the Exploitation Plan is executed in the context of the following considerations:

Feasibility Study: Comprehensive analysis to assess the viability and profitability of the PLOTTO business initiative, including technical, commercial, financial, and organizational evaluations. This aims to understand the potential for PLOTTO's commercialization by analyzing market prospects, financial assumptions, and organizational needs. Success in this stage will lead to further business planning and development steps.

Business Modelling: Utilizing a Business Model Canvas (BMC) approach, this stage defines the business's value proposition, infrastructure, customer segments, and revenue strategies. It emphasizes market positioning and involves all partners and stakeholders to ensure the business model aligns with market needs and project goals.

Business Plan: The business plan for PLOTTO outlines the strategy for market introduction and long-term sustainability. It includes identifying funding opportunities and aims to enhance the market readiness of innovative technologies, reduce market entry barriers, and support the growth of competitive enterprises in Europe, particularly in automated inspection and land-based applications like infrastructure monitoring.

4.1 Key Exploitable Results

Compared to the previous version of the deliverable (D8.2), the list of ERs was updated as follows:

- **Inclusion of two additional ERs:** ER2 – Fast assessment damage maps (satellite, ground sensor and UAV- based) and ER8 – Coupled Multi-nested Local Scale Modelling
- **Update of the ownership structure per ER.**

The previous version of the deliverable (D8.2) included the ER evaluation forms provided by the owners of each ER. Their views regarding the exploitation potential of ERs are a valuable input to the development of the exploitation strategy for the project. Each partner, beyond a high level of technical expertise, has a deep understanding of and a longstanding expertise with relevant markets. The evaluation forms corresponding to the two additional ERs are presented below (Table 6 and Table 7):

Table 6: Fast assessment damage maps (ER2) - Evaluation form

Innovation	Owner	TRL M01	TRL M42
Fast assessment damage maps (satellite, ground sensor and UAV-based)	NTUA, STWS	TRL5	TRL7
Type of Commercial/Business Exploitation			

<p>WP5 aims to develop a commercially viable mapping and damage assessment tool for Inland Waterway (IWW) corridors. This tool will leverage multiple data sources: satellite imagery, ground-based sensors, and Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAS) along with advanced Machine Learning (ML) and Computer Vision (CV) techniques. It will build upon Key Enabling Research (KER) 1 (Enhanced CV and ML) and KER 3 (Multi-sensor data integration) to deliver comprehensive damage detection, mapping, and assessment capabilities.</p> <p>At this stage of the project and based on an initial analysis of the business prospects the exploitation plan of the overall system may include the following options:</p> <p><i>Service Delivery</i>: The overall system could be offered as a service to municipalities, countries and organizations globally. A profitable licensing model tailored to different user needs and scales could be also considered.</p> <p><i>Project-based Deployment</i>: Offer the entire system or its individual advanced algorithms for specific projects based on short- or long-term contracts.</p> <p>These options represent potential pathways based on preliminary analysis. Further evaluation and business plan development will refine the exploitation strategy by the project's final stage.</p>
<p>Exploitation potential</p> <p>The innovation of the envisaged solution lies in its unique combination of novel computer vision and machine learning techniques with multi-sensor data analysis (satellites, vehicles, airborne sensors). This approach enables a dynamic and comprehensive assessment of hazards and resilience to environmental issues. We see significant market potential across various sectors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Infrastructure management: Rapid damage assessment and monitoring of IWW corridors, pipelines, and other critical infrastructure. -Emergency response: Faster and more accurate disaster response, leading to quicker recovery and reduced costs. -Insurance: Improved risk assessment and claims processing through real-time damage mapping. -Environmental monitoring: Early detection and mitigation of environmental hazards like forest fires, floods, and landslides.
<p>Conflicting IP</p> <p>No known conflicting IPs exist at this stage. During the project, we will investigate any conflicting IPs as they arise.</p>
<p>Strengths (<i>What we do well</i>)</p> <p>The IWW monitoring system of PLOT0 under development will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Integrate multi-sensor data and advanced CV & ML algorithms. – Perform flaw and degradation synoptic assessment for different disaster scenarios based on the produced damage maps. – Provide early detection of damage, degradation, and emerging hazards. – Offer rapid post-hazard damage inspection and performance assessment of the assets.
<p>Weaknesses (<i>Are we competitive?</i>)</p> <p>The competitiveness of the IWW mapping and assessment system relies on the extent to which the final product will be deployed. Tech-based solutions form a competitive area for everyone. However, the availability and quality of initial data can impact the accuracy and results of the system.</p>
<p>Opportunities (<i>New stakeholders, Market trends</i>)</p>

Any industry concerned with safety, inspection, and maintenance may benefit from the proposed mapping and assessment system, in addition to operators in the growing market of IWW transportation.
Threats (<i>What are the risks</i>)
The stakeholders and end-users may not be familiar with this technology and as a result the implementation of the system may face some skepticism. Additionally, other competitors can potentially reproduce the solution. UAS products and solutions are frequently subject to rapid technological advancements and innovation, which can render existing products obsolete or outdated. Furthermore, there are several restrictions in various areas concerning UAS flights.
Competition
<i>Other competitive technologies/ products/ solutions</i>
Potential companies/tools/modules that could compete the solution provided by PLOTOTO: -ESRI Damage Assessment tools -CEERISK Bridging the Gap company -The Rapid Damage Assessment (RDA) module of EFFIS -The National Weather Service Damage Assessment Toolkit of the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration -National Alliance for Public Safety GIS (NAPSG) Foundation
Targeted Market
<i>Who are the customers?</i>
-Ministries, Municipalities, and Organizations that manage or exploit IWW and/or the assets included. -IWW and other type of transport operators/authorities. -First/Disaster Responders organizations. -Insurance companies.
Time to Market estimate
After developing the IWW monitoring system, a business plan will be created to explore to the potential commercialization opportunities between M39-M42.
Expected ROI
<i>Initial estimations</i>
TBD
Path to market
<i>How do you plan to embed results in your organisations (i.e. extend the company’s product portfolio, develop new products, etc.)</i>
The NTUA will ensure that the PLOTOTO results and system, as well as the computer vision, will be further diffused and exploited through its networks, products, and research. Additionally, the research conducted during PLOTOTO project will be a valuable addition to the organization’s knowledge domain, resulting in the development of new methods in different or similar scientific areas. Both technical and dissemination activities will assist on that. STWS plans to use IWW monitoring results to expand its safety and security products, including IWW in their critical infrastructure for physical security solutions.

Table 7: Coupled Multi-nested Local Scale Modelling (ER8) - Evaluation form

Innovation	Owner	TRL M01	TRL M42
Coupled Multi-nested Local Scale Modelling	FMI, AUTH	TRL5	TRL8
Type of Commercial/Business Exploitation			
<p>FMI has developed / is developing a computational methodology to generate localized and downscaled wind predictions for targeted pilot sites. Here, the generated datasets are directly utilized by the MHVM toolkit and the exploitation plan is to publicize (to make public) the developed numerical procedure as a potential component of commercial risk-assessment platforms.</p> <p>The following exploitation prospects for the integrated nowcasting / forecasting modelling system developed within the frame of WP3 are foreseen:</p> <p>Further development and application of the system in future research activities and projects at national and international level.</p> <p>Exploitation of the solution for the provision of consulting services and training to potential clients interested in acquiring the system for their own purposes.</p> <p>Improved research and service portfolio of the owners through the potential deployment of the system towards improving the resilience of critical infrastructures against natural and manmade hazards, in view also of potential climate change impacts.</p>			
Exploitation potential			
<p>Commercial operations which are vulnerable to wind-related hazards can gain robustness, preparedness and resilience against weather related uncertainties by utilizing the downscaling innovation developed herein. The benefits pertain to both real-time operational risk monitoring and future projection activities.</p> <p>The product addresses an existing demand which is currently undergoing further development. The market widening has been further enhanced by the legislations imposed by national authorities and European and international organizations (the development of laws and regulations considering climate change control). Significant potential for further exploitation in new research projects and/or provision of a new service in the market, given the existence of an adequate client base and financial/human resources. Business potential will be finalised at later stages of the project via the PLOTO business models and plan.</p>			
Conflicting IP			
<p>FMI and AUTH both develop downscaling procedures for meteorological data but focusing on different spatial scales. FMI targets primarily localized wind-related hazards, thus the two organizations have no overlap in their methodologies.</p> <p>AUTH and FMI, as the two partners mainly responsible for the development of the system in question, act as the core owner of this solution. At this stage of the project, there seems to be no conflicting IP. The core modelling components used by AUTH are distributed as executable files under a proprietary license, while the rest of the modelling components used by FMI as well as the visualisation and data exchange layers are developed based on free software. The IPR management activities will be further clarified during the next phases of the project.</p>			
Strengths (What we do well)			
<p>FMI has the skills, experience and highly efficient modelling tools needed for downscaling large-scale wind fields to local target environments with very high resolution.</p>			

<p>The PLOTO atmospheric modelling system integrates high end – high resolution modelling techniques which focus at the very local scale covering critical infrastructure areas of interest together with operational mesoscale modelling techniques which have the capacity to cover extended areas around the target field sites. The PLOTO atmospheric modelling system is flexible in the sense that it can be easily adjusted towards harmonization with other existing technologies and platforms. In comparison with competitive products and services, the PLOTO atmospheric system offers a more robust and reliable performance at a very high spatial resolution while using process-based models, with their reliability demonstrated in the scientific and technical literature.</p>
<p><i>Weaknesses (Are we competitive?)</i></p> <p>The site-specific model implementation, data acquisition and maintenance may be costly and require a significant investment of time and resources. While the associated processes have been streamlined, the data intensive methodology remains labor-intensive. IWW end-users are often not particularly interested in sophisticated modelling solutions, especially given the current level of economic crisis and in many cases, they cannot fully comprehend exactly what the generated modelling data represent.</p> <p>The modelling system is normally operated and maintained by highly skilled – highly trained staff. While efforts have been made to employ visualization and configuration layers in the form of a GUI, there are still configurational aspects of the system that will need to be handled by specialized operators.</p> <p>Potential reliability issues related to maintenance exist. For example, in cases of power surge or in cases when the installed sensors on site stop transmitting data. Depending on the availability demands of end-users, the system could be supplanted by hardware and software mitigation to increase availability and reduce downtime.</p>
<p><i>Opportunities (New stakeholders, Market trends)</i></p> <p>The wind-downscaling methodology developed by FMI can be relatively easily adapted to other application areas outside the IWW infrastructure field. Therefore, the scope of exploitation opportunities and number of potential stakeholders is large. There is a trend of increasing interest towards improving resilience against climatological threats, hazards and vulnerabilities in numerous sectors of societies and businesses.</p> <p>Successful implementation may be applicable to other applications, such as utilities, etc.</p> <p>Emerging markets: developing countries have funding available for similar projects, thanks to banks and programs for development.</p> <p>May open up markets also in the US and Asia (e.g. through international partnerships).</p> <p>Besides, potential partnerships include the possibility of establishing permanent cooperation with international or European institutes. More specifically, the modelling system can be combined with other models, on the basis of developing a large-scale observatory for cities, which would help air quality or climate change control and would allow more efficient policy making.</p>
<p><i>Threats (What are the risks)</i></p> <p>The wind downscaling methodology needs detailed input data sets such as digital terrain models, digital surface models and land-use maps in high resolution. Such data is becoming increasingly available, but in some cases, especially in developing countries, the necessary data may not be available. The wind downscaling also needs a considerable amount of work by highly skilled personnel. Thus, lack of availability of suitable personnel is a potential threat. The third prerequisite is the availability of sufficient high-performance computing power, thus lack of it is seen as a potential threat.</p>

<p>In terms of the scientific knowledge needed for the development of the system there already exist other competitors mainly from the US and East Asia who are equally strong. There is a risk that big companies – players at a worldwide level will seek to suppress initiatives in this field which are normally driven mostly by SMEs. The threat is partially mitigated by existing legislative and cultural barriers that up to now have inhibited wide adoption of such products.</p>
<p>Competition <i>Other competitive technologies/ products/ solutions</i></p>
<p>Consultancy sector where low-accuracy solutions are marketed as viable alternatives. To the best of our knowledge, the main competition revolves around US and East Asian-based products / solutions. Competition is also expected from low-cost IWW-oriented platforms that are rapidly deployed based on surrogate (not processed-based) models. These systems have demonstrably worse performance compared to the PLOTTO solution, especially in predicting extreme events, however they are marketed as an attractive alternative due to the small deployment cost and time.</p>
<p>Targeted Market <i>Who are the customers?</i></p>
<p>The potential target customers are the integrated operators of critical infrastructures such IWW, road transport, ports, power generation and water facilities. Software developers providing risk-assessment solutions for such operators.</p> <p>The product is addressed to the European and global market. Potential users are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • research organizations that deal with issues of environment, climate change, air quality etc., such as the European Environment Agency (EEA), OECD, Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), World Health Organization, World Meteorological Organization (WMO), the International Institute for Sustainable Development etc. • local stakeholders, such as governmental agencies, local and regional authorities and city planners in order to evaluate scenarios regarding the effect of urban planning policies (the establishment of manufacturing zones, the urbanization of specific areas etc.) on the air quality and wind flow or for emergency planning in cases of accidental chemical releases (e.g. fires or spills of hazardous materials). • enterprises, for undertaking environmental impact assessment of their industrial facilities or for emergency planning assessment (e.g. for chemical industries). <p>Given the aforementioned characteristics of the target market related to the modelling system, the potential customers could contain the integrated operators of critical infrastructures such IWW, road transport, ports, power generation and water facilities.</p>
<p>Time to Market estimate</p>
<p>Following the completion of the final version of the numerical framework and the subsequent integration into the overall PLOTTO risk-assessment platform, a business plan to investigate potential commercialization and/or utilization in further applications will be prepared. A pre-commercial version of the solution is expected 1 to 3 years after the project's end.</p> <p>Following the release of the final version of the modelling system in question and its integration into the overall PLOTTO platform, a business plan to investigate potential commercialization and/or utilization in further research activities will be prepared. A pre-commercial version of the solution is expected 1 to 3 years after the project's end.</p>

Expected ROI <i>Initial estimations</i>
TBD
Path to market <i>How do you plan to embed results in your organisations (i.e. extend the company’s product portfolio, develop new products, etc.)</i>
<p>Our goal at FMI is to become the leading provider of state-of-the-art high-resolution data for wind-related risk assessment and analysis solutions. Our strategy is to offer datasets in a portable and scalable manner which enables partner organizations to exploit them efficiently in novel applications.</p> <p>All consortium partners will ensure that the PLOT0 results will be further diffused and exploited through their networks and products. The partners will also seek to exploit further components that can be individually or, through collaborations within the consortium, sold to interested customers. Finally, as through their participation in PLOT0, the partners will reinforce their product portfolio, addressing solutions for the maritime sector.</p> <p>The AUTH team is currently in contact with the Technology Transfer Office (TTO) of the University (http://rc.auth.gr/tto, page in Greek) to identify pathways to valorization and commercial exploitation of the system. Based on our previous experience, AUTH/TTO can effectively support the conversion of research results into patents and licenses that can be used in service contracts and bilateral license agreements.</p>

In the context of Deliverable 8.3 the ERs were evaluated for the purpose of selecting the KERs of the project. First, partners’ business views indicated if they perceive their result as KER based on their opinions and exploitation strategies. Second, the result’s market needs based on the project’s current analysis.

Key Exploitable Results respond to a specific customer need and aims at satisfying the respective demand. A key exploitable result (KER) is a term used in the context of the European Commission’s Horizon Europe programme, which funds research and innovation projects. According to the Horizon Results Platform, a KER is: *an identified main interesting result, which has been selected and prioritised due to its high potential to be “exploited” – meaning to make use and derive benefits- downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education.* . It is important to keep in mind that Key Exploitable Results are not final market-ready products.

The aforementioned changes are presented in the following table (Table 8):

Table 8: Updated ER list

ER #	Asset/ER	Owner	KER
1	Enhanced Computer vision for damage diagnosis and ML techniques	NTUA	
2	Fast assessment damage maps (satellite, ground sensor and UAV- based)	NTUA, STWS	YES
3	Seamless integration of data from multiple sensors on UAVs, fixed ground stations and moving vehicles for damage mapping and monitoring	STWS	

4	IWW Simulators with climate scenarios and new data emanating from the project outcomes	All technical partners	
5	Multi-Hazard Vulnerability Modules and Assessment Toolkit for IWW	SORECC, NTUA	
6	COP and IMS, adapted to PLOTO needs and selected scenarios	STWS	
7	Middleware and Data Fusion Services	RISA	YES
8	Coupled Multi-nested Local Scale Modelling	AUTH, FMI	
9	Fore-Now/Casting Weather Predictions tool	AUTH, FMI	YES
10	Integrated PLOTO platform	All technical partners	YES
11	Risk Assessment Engine	NTUA	YES
12	Software for assessing socioeconomic impact	SORECC	YES
13	River Digital Twin	EXUS	

4.2 Individual exploitation plans

In Table 9, the individual exploitation plans for PLOTO are presented, with updates to the initial version when applicable. They are expected to be further refined once the project reaches a later stage of maturity.

Table 9: Individual exploitation plans at the start of the project

Partner	Exploitation Plans
INTRA & INTRA-LU	INTRA expects to gain high knowledge on the PLOTO topics and enhance further its visibility. PLOTO results will be further diffused and exploited in INTRA's network and products. INTRA will also seek to further exploit components (with a focus on the integrated PLOTO platform) that can be individually or in collaboration with the other consortium partners, sold to interested customers. Finally, as through its participation in PLOTO will reinforce its solutions portfolio addressing solutions for the Maritime sector.
EXUS	EXUS will exploit (either independently, or jointly in the suite of tools that will be developed in the project) the Digital Twin solution. EXUS will also use the knowledge obtained in developing the PLOTO ML based prediction models, to increase its TRL through national or EU funding initiatives in other domains of security and/or crisis response. In addition, EXUS ML based prediction models are part of the implementation roadmap of EXUS Analytics Framework (EAF) and the EXUS AI Technologies (EXAITE), which is a major mid-term commercial milestone that will ensure its greater scaling-up and financial viability. EXUS foresees to utilize the developed methodology or parts of the algorithms that are relevant in its FinTech product called EFS and commercialize it as a new feature via its sales network in 35 countries worldwide
FMI	The regional climate modelling method with downscaling in several steps to the local level is expected to be a major outcome of the project that will also be used for other purposes where site-specific information is needed after the project. Additional CORDEX simulations performed within the project will be published through the CORDEX data nodes and thereby made available for a wider user community.
NTUA	NTUA expects to gain high knowledge on above topics and enhance their visibility by collaborating with strategic industrial partners of the consortium in the field of resilience of IWW and hinterland infrastructures. PLOTO results will be exploited by postdoc, PhD students and research team involved in PLOTO. Research-wise, NTUA will gain experience and increase their reputation through the project and will make it

	easier for NTUA to successfully participate in future related R&D projects, thus increasing their resources. The presentation of NTUA R&D achievements to public conferences are a further target that will reinforce and expand NTUA existence in the field.
RISA	RISA will exploit the results of the project on a commercial basis by means of enhancing its existing platforms for the provision of enhanced data management, visualisation systems and decision support services. PLOTO comes as a natural continuation of RISA's recent work within various projects dealing with the development of such platforms. As a minimum, RISA expects the PLOTO project to: a) advance the development of its data management and decision support software products and participation in more national projects concerning IWW protection, b) raise the profile of RISA's capability in the challenging IWW protection systems market, c) support the employment and development of engineering skills in Germany, d) provide an adaptive platform that could be used with small changes targeting other vertical business sectors. e) develop RISA as a valued contributor to European framework projects further, and f) further propagate the IT and engineering standards used in the PLOTO at a local and international level.
AUTH	Exploitation includes the population of EU climate databases with high resolution data. These data will be available to the scientific community and the relevant stakeholders who participate in policy making. AUTH will also exploit the downscaling toolset and methodologies for enhancing its placement as a provider of climate services. The developed know-how and modelling tools are expected to become part of a multiscale simulation platform for providing focused risk assessment and management services.
SoReCC	PLOTO's final core product, shall be used in relevant advisory assignments to organisations across Europe and beyond. All results shall also be presented to public international conference where SoReCC is actively participating for many years now, promoting the resilience concept globally. Additionally, SoReCC is communicating its work via social media to the general public and via publications to the scientific communities.
DBC	Expansion of existing services: DBC currently provides exploitation services in a number of key areas in Greece. DBC envisages an opportunity to expand their market offerings once the PLOTO innovations are developed. In addition, the knowledge that DBC's involvement in PLOTO will be valuable to expand their market penetration in these activities. DBC sees the potential to be involved in future related R&D and IA projects through their involvement in the PLOTO project. DBC anticipates that if funded PLOTO will develop IP that can be utilized to facilitate the development of new businesses and DBC are highly motivated to be part of such developments.
BME	The results will be available to the scientific community and the relevant stakeholders who participate in policy making. The knowledge will be utilized during study-aid developments. PLOTO results will be exploited by postdoc, PhD students BME will gain experience and reputation through the project which facilitates the participations in future related R&D projects.
ULIEGE	The innovative inundation mapping methodology, combining high resolution climate data and stochastic dike breach modelling, will be a major outcome of the project, which may subsequently be replicated at multiple other locations in Europe for upgrading flood risk maps. Similarly, advances in image-based monitoring of infrastructure will pave the way for new applications in other waterways. PLOTO results will be further exploited by PhD students, postdocs and master students at ULIEGE.
UDG	PLOTO will allow UDG to work closely with industry and countries involved to support partnerships in critical areas such as IWW transport. The R&D results will be exploited

	by postdoc, PhD students and research team and will be available to the scientific community and the relevant stakeholders PLOTTO will be key to leveraging public and private collaboration, to foster the implementation of new technologies, sustainable innovations and spread successful new resilience solutions across Europe and the world.
RRT	Similarly, advances in image-based monitoring of infrastructure will pave the way for new applications in other waterways. PLOTTO results will be available for tailored solutions to address the needs of other ports, as for example the ports of Braila and Tulcea.
STWS	STWS develops integrated Geospatial C2C solutions for Security and Public Safety applications and for customers such as police, coast guard, etc. It also develops DSS for natural hazards crisis management. PLOTTO will help further enhance its position in the public safety market, enhance its portfolio in the domain of crisis management tools for planning and provide an opportunity for demonstration to international stakeholders. In PLOTTO, ENGAGE will be used to create the situational picture; prove the opportunity for synergies with other partners to jointly promote related developments as an integrated product. The following actions to support efficient exploitation and commercial utilization are foreseen after the end of PLOTTO: a) Marketing and Sales efforts via trade fairs, exhibitions; specific marketing initiatives to address new customers, b) sales activities via our distribution network, c) active participation in industrial seminars to communicate selected exploitable results.
UM	Partners of European associations (OpenEnloCC, EPTS) are heavily involved in activities related to IWW resilience to climate change and other extreme events. The methods and tools developed within the PLOTTO project will improve the existing solutions of the University of Maribor in the field of Earth observation. An Earth observation satellite owned by the University of Maribor will be used for the project to prove its feasibility.
ERTC	ERTICO focusses among others on facilitating the deployment of future solutions for the Freight transport and logistics sectors, to enable the Sustainable management of goods, and freight flows. Hence, ERTICO will raise awareness among the respective ERTICO partners and end-users about the project solutions aiming at the integration of the PLOTTO technologies in future projects and activities where these are key enablers. Project Technologies will be also promoted through ERTICO Academy and synergies, regarding the project innovations will be developed with partners of relevant ERTICO projects and through the ERTICO partnership and start-up ecosystem.
End-users	All end-users (i.e. port, authorities, railway) will cooperate in organizing a meeting with stakeholders to support the extension of PLOTTO to other IWW cases. AFDJ: The PLOTTO results, will allow AFDJ to perform a better intervention plan for navigation along the Maritime Danube (Braila to Sulina). As beginning of the project, AFDJ was a source of hydrometeorological data (Use Case A) and by the end, the PLOTTO platform, could be an input for specific AFDJ Department, to issue Notice to Skipper, when necessary. Further, the Notice to Skipper, will be publish, to AFDJ website and specific navigational platform (Danube FIS Portal, etc.).

5 IPR Management

The PLOT0 project aims at the development of a platform that will help increase the resilience of the Inland Water Ways (IWW) infrastructures and the connected land infrastructures, thus ensuring reliable network availability under unfavourable conditions, such as extreme weather, accidents and other kind of hazards. The main target of the project is to combine downscaled climate change scenarios (applied to IWW infrastructures) with simulation tools and actual data, so as to provide the relevant authorities and their operators with an integrated tool able to support more effective management of their infrastructures at strategic and operational levels. As a result of the project activities, various components will be developed and become an integral part of the platform and their exploitation is considered a matter of outmost importance.

5.1 IPR Strategy

Following the recommendations of the grant agreement related to the exploitation of the developed components during the course and as a result of the project, taking also into consideration the intellectual property (IP) related legislation and rights, the conduction of IP related agreements is foreseen as the proper tool of allocation and protection of ownership.

For this purpose, the following matters shall be identified and examined throughout the IPR allocation process:

- a. Identification of the components developed as a result of the PLOT0 project.
- b. Management of the aforementioned components.
- c. Cases of joint ownership.
- d. Protection of the aforementioned components from unauthorized use.
- f. The way the aforementioned components will be exploited.

The aforementioned IPR related agreements will most probably be signed during the final stages of the project, following the actual development of the components of the platform. With these agreements, matters related to the accurate and appropriate allocation of the IP ownership to the partners, according to their actual contribution, will be addressed, while simultaneously the exploitation rights, royalties and strategy and the type of IPR protection (e.g. Patent, trademark etc.) will be defined.

5.1.1 Definitions

For the purposes of understanding of key terms related to the IP management and the IPR rights, the following definitions are provided:

1. **“Intellectual Property”** is intangible property resulting from creations of the mind. It falls into 2 categories: i) industrial property, such as patents on new inventions, trademarks, designs and models, as well as service brands and protected designations of origin and ii) copy right and related rights, such as music, literature, paintings and sculptures¹.

¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/EN/legal-content/glossary/intellectual-property.html>

2. **“Intellectual Property rights”** are those that allow owners - creators as inventors or artists or any rightsholders to decide how, when and where their creations are used and/or exploited².
3. **“Grant agreement”** refers to the one signed and related to project - PLOTO, as it stands up to the day of conduction of this deliverable or may be amended in the future.
4. **“Consortium agreement”** refers to the one signed by the partners of the PLOTO project, as it stands up to the day of conduction of this deliverable or may be amended in the future.

5.1.2 Intellectual property plan methodology

The first step of ensuring proper IPR allocation is the collection of the necessary information from the partners. The partners were requested to provide all the necessary information regarding the components that will be developed with their collaboration, their projected ownership and their development status (pending or completed).

Their input was included in the PLOTO KERs tool that was created on excel form. The results developed during the project were all identified as key exploitable results and are presented in the aforementioned tool. Information regarding the type of licence for utilization, the related KPIs, the key metrics used to evaluate the performance of each ER, alongside with a short description, financial predictions (expenses / revenue) and the status of development of the components are also provided in detail.

Following the collection of the input from the partners, we will be able to identify any conflicts between the partners in terms of the IPR allocation. In case any issues as such may arise, the authorized partner will seek even more detailed information regarding the related exploitable result, engage to meetings and calls between the related partners and the project coordinator and consult any other relative body needed in order to ensure that the conflict will cease to exist.

Finally, in case any conflicts are avoided or resolved as part of the competent partners' actions, the allocation of the IPR will take place via the conduction of IPR agreements.

5.1.3 Knowledge management framework

Apart from the collection of the necessary information, a matter that is addressed in the following sections and will be finalized in deliverable 8.4 is the identification of the proper legal framework, relatable to the protection of the project's key exploitable results. As a result, in subsection 5.5, detailed information is provided regarding matters such as:

1. The access rights to the key exploitable results,
2. The ownership of the key exploitable results,
3. The case of joint ownership,
4. The way the ownership could be transferred,
5. Protection of the key exploitable results,
6. The exploitation of the results and
7. The relatable publications.

² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/EN/legal-content/glossary/intellectual-property.html>

5.2 Types of knowledge

5.2.1 Background

According to the Consortium agreement and Article 16.1 of the Grant Agreement, background is defined as “data, know-how or information that is needed to implement the action or exploit the results”.

The Background provided by specific partners for the project related purposes of PLOTO is presented in attachment 1 of the consortium agreement. Moreover, references are being made to the specific restrictions and/or conditions for implementation and exploitation of the provided background. This information is a key indicator of the cooperation of each partner to the developed exploitable result and as a result, its participation.

5.2.2 Exploitable results

This term refers to the results that will be developed as a result of the project related activities. According to the term provided in article 16.2 of the Grant agreement, results means “any tangible or intangible effect of the action, such as data, know-how or information, whatever its form or nature, whether or not it can be protected, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights”. The overall list of the results is presented in tables 8 and 9 below.

The partners have identified the key exploitable results during the collection of the information by DBC. The criteria chosen during the evaluation process were the level of innovation, exploitability and impact of the result. As key exploitable results, the “Fast assessment damage maps (satellite, ground sensor and UAV- based)”, the “Middleware and Data Fusion Services”, the “Fore-Now/Casting Weather Predictions tool”, the “Integrated PLOTO platform”, the “Risk Assessment Engine” and the “Software for assessing socioeconomic impact” were identified.

The partners provided their input related to the identification of the exploitable results to be developed for the purposes of the project. For the purposes of proper allocation of the IPR, the partners shall maintain any documentation and evidence in general, in order to be able to provide the necessary information regarding their participation in the development of each exploitable result, thus ensuring that proper and accurate allocation of the IPR is achieved, according to any applicable laws and conditions.

This is deemed to be a matter of utmost importance, especially in the case of joint ownership or in case any conflicts may arise during the allocation process. The partners shall proceed to the necessary actions with the assistance of DBC in order for Joint ownerships agreements to be signed in order for the exploitation activities to take place. They shall provide all the necessary documentation and feedback to DBC and the rest of the parties involved in those agreements in order to prove their level of participation in the development of the results and the proper allocation of IPRs to be established. This procedure will be reported in any way applicable, including but not limited to, periodic project reports, deliverable 8.4 or any other official project related document.

Moreover, in case employees of any partner or any other personnel or third party are intitled to claim rights on the exploitable results, the partner shall ensure that a relative agreement has been conducted in order for the partner to be able to meet its contractual obligations. In such cases, the authorized partners in charge of the IPR allocation shall be informed in order to proceed to all the necessary additional actions required.

The process of identification, definition and allocation of the exploitable results will be an ongoing process until the end of the PLOTO project and DBC will proceed to all the necessary procedures in order to ensure proper allocation of the IPR.

5.2.3 Record of intellectual property assets

The first step of identification of **ownership** of the results and allocation of the IPR is the identification of the results to be developed during the course of the project. In the PLOTO KERs tool, the partners provided the following key exploitable results (Table 10), which are presented alongside with the relevant project KPIs (see Annex A):

Table 10: ER - KPI correspondence

#	Name of the Exploitable result	Relevant project KPI
1	Enhanced Computer vision for damage diagnosis and ML techniques	KPI 3, KPIs 19-22
2	Fast assessment damage maps (satellite, ground sensor and UAV-based)	KPI 3, KPIs 19-22
3	Seamless integration of data from multiple sensors on UAVs, fixed ground stations and moving vehicles for damage mapping and monitoring	KPI 3, KPIs 19-22
4	IWW Simulators with climate scenarios and new data emanating from the project outcomes	KPI 1
5	Multi-Hazard Vulnerability Modules and Assessment Toolkit for IWW	KPI 7
6	COP and IMS, adapted to PLOTO needs and selected scenarios	KPI 5, KPIs 23-27
7	Middleware and Data Fusion Services	KPIs 8-18
8	Coupled Multi-nested Local Scale Modelling	KPI 1
9	Fore-Now/Casting Weather Predictions tool	KPI 2
10	Integrated PLOTO platform	KPI 6, KPI 28
11	Risk Assessment Engine	KPI 4, KPI 6, KPI 7
12	Software for assessing socioeconomic impact	KPI 6
13	River Digital Twin	KPI 4

5.3 Ownership schemas and IPR matrix

Alongside the presentation of the exploitable results, a reference was made to the project partners who will declare ownership of the exploitable results. In terms of joint ownership of the exploitable results, the communication between the joint owners will be started in order for the ownership schemas to be defined and any disputes to be addressed according to the provisions of the CA. The procedure will be reported in any way applicable, including but not limited to, periodic project reports or any other official project related document and the final results will be presented in deliverable D8.4. According to the information received, the ownership of the results is the following (Table 11):

Table 11: ER-declared owner correspondence

#	Name of the Exploitable result	Declared Owner(s)
1	Enhanced Computer vision for damage diagnosis and ML techniques	NTUA

2	Fast assessment damage maps (satellite, ground sensor and UAV-based)	NTUA, STWS
3	Seamless integration of data from multiple sensors on UAVs, fixed ground stations and moving vehicles for damage mapping and monitoring	STWS
4	IWW Simulators with climate scenarios and new data emanating from the project outcomes	INTRA, NTUA
5	Multi-Hazard Vulnerability Modules and Assessment Toolkit for IWW	SORECC, NTUA
6	COP and IMS, adapted to PLOTO needs and selected scenarios	STWS
7	Middleware and Data Fusion Services	RISA
8	Coupled Multi-nested Local Scale Modelling	AUTH, FMI
9	Fore-Now/Casting Weather Predictions tool	AUTH, FMI
10	Integrated PLOTO platform	INTRA, NTUA
11	Risk Assessment Engine	NTUA
12	Software for assessing socioeconomic impact	SORECC
13	River Digital Twin	EXUS

5.4 Instruments for project results protection

The development of the exploitable results is of course the purpose of the project and such development shall be protected by the implementation of any legal measure that will ensure proper and successful protection of the IPR. As a result, we have proceeded to the identification of the proper legal requirements needed to be implemented in the case of the PLOTO project in order to ensure proper protection of the IPR of the partners developing the exploitable results.

Patent

An applicable protection measure is patent. Patents are exclusive rights granted for a new technical invention that provides its owner the legal right to exclude others from producing, using in any way or selling it for a period of time in exchange for publishing an enabling disclosure of the invention. A patent holder can grant a licence to somebody wishing to produce copies of the invention against payment of a fee (or royalty), thus obtaining a return on the investment.

There is a foreseen procedure related to the patent application and acquisition. It could take place in either national or regional patent offices (e.g. the European Patent Office (EPO)), with the geographical scope of protection of the invention defining the selection of the competent regional authority. An application for a European Patent at the EPO though, still requires validation at national offices to benefit from the protection.

A patent applicant must provide the competent Office with all the necessary information in a sufficient, clear and complete manner, in order for the invention to be carried out by a person skilled in the art (in so-called “patent claims”). The term of a patent is of 20 years from the date of filling of the application. A standard essential patent (SEPs) is a patent essential to implement a specific industry standard or technical solution.

In order for a patent to be granted, the following procedures shall be followed as part of the European patent granting procedure:

- A European patent application consists of a request for grant, a description of the invention, claims, drawings (if any), an abstract. It can be filed in English, German or French without the need of a translation and can be done either virtually or on paper. Following the filing of the application, there is a one month period for the initial fee to be paid.
- The applicant shall proceed to an assessment to identify whether all the necessary information and documentation have been provided, so that the application can be accorded a filing date. The possibility of identification of the applicant and the detailed description of the invention are key factors in this case.
- Following the successful filing of the application, a European search report will be drawn up, listing all the documents available to the Office that may be relevant to assessing novelty and inventive step. The search report is based on the patent claims but also considers the description and any drawings. Immediately after it has been drawn up, the search report is sent to the applicant together with a copy of any cited documents and an initial opinion as to whether the claimed invention and the application meet the requirements of the European Patent Convention.
- The next step is the publication of the application in the European patent office. This action will take place in 18 months, following the filing date of the application. Early publication could be requested. This procedure ensures that potential customers, investors or third parties in general are informed regarding the pending application.
- Examination whether the patent could be granted. In this procedure, the decision is made whether a patent could be granted, with regards to the information that are available to the EPO and any objections filed. In case the aforementioned objections cannot be overcome, the EPO will refuse the application and the applicant can always appeal against this decision.
- If the examining division decides that a patent can be granted, it issues a decision to that effect. A mention of the grant is published in the European Patent Bulletin once the translations of the claims have been filed and the fee for grant and publication have been paid. The decision to grant takes effect on the date of publication. The granted European patent is a "bundle" of individual national patents.
- Once the mention of the grant is published, the patent must be validated in each of the designated states within a specific time limit to retain its protective effect and be enforceable against infringers. In several contracting states, the patent owner may have to file a translation of the specification in an official language of the national patent office. Depending on the relevant national law, the applicant may also have to pay fees by a certain date.
- After the European patent has been granted, it may be opposed by third parties – usually the applicant's competitors – if they believe that it should not have been granted. This could be on the grounds, for example, that the invention lacks novelty or does not involve an inventive step. Notice of opposition can only be filed within nine months of the grant being mentioned in the European Patent Bulletin. Oppositions are dealt with by opposition divisions, which are normally made up of three examiners.
- This stage may also consist of revocation or limitation proceedings initiated by the patent proprietor himself. At any time after the grant of the patent, the patent proprietor may request the revocation or limitation of his patent. The decision to limit or to revoke the European patent takes effect on the date on which it is published in the European Patent Bulletin and applies ab initio to all contracting states in respect of which the patent was granted.

- Decisions of the European Patent Office – refusing an application or in opposition cases, for example – are open to appeal. Decisions on appeals are taken by the independent boards of appeal. In certain cases, it may be possible to file a petition for review by the Enlarged Board of Appeal³.

Copyright

Copyright is a type of intellectual property that provides exclusive rights to a developer / author / creator to make copies, license, and otherwise exploit a creative work in a literary, artistic, educational, or musical form. Copyright is intended to protect the original expression of an idea in the form of a creative work, but not the idea itself. The requirement of originality essentially means that a work must reflect the author's personality, i.e. whether he/she has been able to express his/her own creativity by making free choices. It also implies an intellectual effort from the author. Contrary to patents and trademarks, copyright protection is automatic and not granted by a particular governmental institution. It should be kept in mind that copyright law is not harmonized, which means that the principle of territoriality applies. As a result, protection in one region or country does not automatically extend to the rest of the world. In Europe, copyright protection lasts for the lifetime of the author of the work, plus an additional 70 years after the death of the author.

Trademark

The term trademark refers to a recognizable insignia, phrase, word, or symbol that denotes a specific product and legally differentiates it from all other products of its kind. A trademark exclusively identifies a product as belonging to a specific company and recognizes the company's ownership of the brand. As indicators of business origin, trademarks can be words, logos, devices or other distinctive features, or a combination of these.

Trademark owners may prevent third parties from using, during trade, identical or similar signs for goods or services which are identical or similar to those registered for a trademark, when such use would result in a likelihood of confusion. Like patents, trademarks must generally be registered at national or regional offices. The application for a trademark at a national or regional office means that the geographical scope of protection of the sign will differ. There are 6 steps to register a trademark in the EU:

- i. Trademark search in order to define whether a similar mark has already been registered in the EU before you begin the task of applying with the EUIPO.
- ii. In case there is no similar registration, we can proceed with the filing of a trademark application.
- iii. In case additional information are required by the EUIPO, the applicant shall provide them without undue delay.
- iv. In case the application process was successful, the trademark will be published in the EU Trademark Bulletin.
- v. In case no oppositions have been filed, the EUIPO will finally approve the trademark.

³ <https://www.epo.org/en/new-to-patents/how-to-apply-for-a-patent>

A trademark registered in the EU is valid for 10 years from the date it is issued. The trademark rights must be renewed every 10 years in order to be maintained.

Trade secret

Trade secrets may include a vast amount of information and know-how that is not protectable or cannot be protected properly through patents, such as early-stage inventions, manufacturing processes and/or lists of suppliers and clients. A proper way of trade secrets' protection is the signing of non-disclosure agreement, which may not provide total protection in terms of disclosure but in any way create certain rights and obligations to the parties involved, thus providing compensation to an affected party by a relative violation of the agreement.

In order for valuable information on technology or on any other aspect to be properly protected and considered as trade secrets, the following condition shall be met:

- i. The information should not be publicly available at large or by the experts of the sector in question.
- ii. The information has commercial value and
- iii. Necessary steps to keep the information secret shall be followed such as the conduction of non-disclosure agreements with everybody who has access to it in any way.

5.5 Management of knowledge and project results protection

Access Rights

The term Access rights refers to the permissions an individual user in our case holds to read, write, modify, delete or otherwise access the result.

The treatment of Access Rights is presented in section 9 of the Consortium Agreement and section 2 article 16 of chapter 4 of the Grant agreement. The use of Exploitable Results as well as Background data will be limited restrictively to the necessary project related operations and in accordance with the level of access granted. Access rights shall be free of any additional expenses unless otherwise applicable in relevant intellectual property laws and regulations. All requests for Access Rights shall be made in writing.

Access rights to other entities whose activities fall within the scope of the background or the exploitable results process and aim at exploiting the results of each party concerned should be exercised under the circumstances of territorial perspective and the relation with the other Parties.

The access rights to the background are foreseen in "attachment 1" of the Consortium agreement. Each partner contributing with background to the project, has provided detailed restrictions regarding their use by the rest of the partners and/or third parties and exploitation. The partners are obliged to respect the forementioned guidelines set out by the partners in case of restriction of access in order to avoid any issues and communicate with the partner – owner of the background in case it is needed for the background to be utilized in the project related activities.

Regarding the access rights to the exploitable results, different conditions are implemented. As a general rule, access rights to exploitable results in terms of exploitation shall be granted on fair and reasonable conditions, whether financial or not (section 9.4.1 of the Consortium agreement).

Furthermore, in section 9 of the consortium agreement, provisions are foreseen that are related to:

- i. The inclusion of new partners in the project consortium
- ii. Exclusion in any way and for any legitimate reason of any partner from the project consortium
- iii. Teaching activities for the purposes of the project

Finally, in subsection 9.8, specific provisions regarding access rights to software are foreseen in the case of exploitable results, apart from the already foreseen general provisions. In such case, access to Object Code and, if it necessary, access to an Application Programming Interface (API) and/or Source Code should be ensured. On the other hand, background shall only be provided in Object Code or API unless agreed otherwise between the partners.

Results ownership

The term ownership refers to the state or fact of legal possession and control over property, which may be any asset, tangible or intangible.

The ownership of the exploitable results is foreseen in article 8 of the Consortium Agreement and section 2, article 16.2 in the Grant Agreement. As a general rule, the exploitable results are owned by the project partner who generates them. The granting authority does not hold ownership of the results that are produced. Results are owned by the party that generates them.

Joint ownership

Two or more parties could hold joint ownership if they have together produced the result, or it is not possible to verify which party has contributed and to what extent to the result. The joint ownership must be defined in written form, with references to the percentage of ownership of each owner, so that explicit clearance regarding the shared activities is ensured. Joint ownership agreements will be conducted that will ensure proper allocation of the IPR. The definition of the partners that will be joint owners in an exploitable result and the tasks that each one has undertaken during the development procedure are matters of outmost importance from the early stages of the project.

If joint ownership cannot be identified in detail, the party that contributes to an activity resulting in this situation, must contact the other to ensure the possibility of joint ownership. The joint owners should discuss internally all the issues related to and arising from this relationship including matters of costs, filing applications for Intellectual Property Rights etc.

In case of any disputes related to this matter, the issue will be resolved by the PCT who will report to the Plenary Board for final decision, or as per article 11.8 of the consortium agreement, in case the conflict cannot be solved amicably. Of course, any applicable European or national legislation will be respected during this process.

In the case of PLOTTO, joint ownership has been identified in some exploitable results and the necessary measures will be implemented in order to ensure proper IPR allocation and management.

Transfer of results

The transfer of exploitable results is also addressed in section 8.3 of the Consortium Agreement. The partners have the right to transfer ownership of their own results as well as their share on joint ownership results unless different provisions are met by virtue of other applicable laws, regulations, or agreement. The obligation of noticing other parties of the transferring is applicable as well as the

noticing of other Parties regarding the access rights is crucial. The other parties have the right to object to this transfer, demonstrating it could end up harmful for their activity.

Granting licenses

The partners can grant licenses to their results or give the right for exploitation. Exclusive licenses for results may be granted only if the other beneficiaries are not interested in exercising their right of access anymore. Specific terms are also provisioned for access rights to software (controlled license terms).

Exploitation of results

The overall exploitation of the results strategy is described in the Grant Agreement. It includes a total of several exploitation activities such as:

- i. a comprehensive stakeholder analysis,
- ii. a business plan,
- iii. market consideration and financial projections
- iv. a risk management analysis and
- v. the alignment with other relevant projects - activities

Publication notification procedure

In section 8.4.2 of the Consortium Agreement, the process to be followed is described, in order for a project related publication of the results to take place. According to this section, a prior notice of 45 calendar days should be given to other parties before any publication. Objections should always be filed in a written form within 30 calendar days from the receipt of the publication and if no objection has taken place, then the publication is permitted.

6 Inland waterway transport (IWT) in Europe

The **Inland Waterway Transport (IWT) market** involves all the direct potential adopters of the integrated PLOT solution. The current section refers to the current state and prospects of the IWT market in the **European area**. IWT offers an **efficient alternative to railway and road transport**, complements supply chains involving overseas transport, and depending on the origin and destination of the transport flows, it competes with maritime transport companies (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Transport chain exemplar, Source: Assessment of potential of maritime and inland ports and inland waterways, Final Report, European Commission, 2020

Inland waterway resilience is central to the smooth operation of the transport chain. Failing to detect vulnerabilities and damages to the inland waterway network will lead to a disruption of both the **maritime pre-haul and post-haul**, generating **cascade effects throughout the transport chain**. Therefore, the stakeholders of this inland waterway market have a direct interest in PLOT, as it allows them to **take timely action and mitigate risks** stemming from the inland waterway conditions and transport operations. In the subsections that follow, insights pertaining to the inland waterway market will be presented, with the aim of **uncovering the customer needs that PLOT aspires to satisfy**.

6.1 IWT market stakeholders

Direct users of IWT - inland waterway transport companies

Indirect users of IWT - freight forwarders and hauliers

Regulatory and administrative control authorities of IWW corridor (national & regional)

Figure 4: IWT market stakeholders

The **inland waterway market is the key market targeted by PLOTO** and therefore, identifying the main market stakeholders (Figure 4) is a crucial step to **ensure Key Exploitable Results align with their characteristics and respond adequately to their needs**. The first stakeholder category referenced refers to inland waterway transport companies. These **companies' viability and profitability** depend on the **state of and accessibility of inland waterways**. Efficient and continuous monitoring of the inland waterway transport network and associated infrastructures, as well as fast damage assessment throughout the transport network, are essential prerequisites for their smooth operation. According to Eurostat for 2020, there are **5486 IWW freight transport companies active in the European area**⁴. Also, **88%** of these companies are registered in a country crossed by the **Rhine**. The biggest Inland Water Freight Transport Companies in Europe ⁵are: Bayliner, Bénéteau Group, CMA CGM Group, Construction Navale Bordeaux and DFDS. Other companies operating in this market are: European Cruise Service, EURO-RIJN B.V., MEYER WERFT GmbH & Co., KG, MSC Mediterranean Shipping Company S.A and Rhenus Group. **Indirect users of inland waterway transportation** such as **freight forwarders and hauliers**, are less dependable upon the state of inland waterways given that they can arrange freight transfer via alternative roots. Nevertheless, facilitated access to **information about traffic, state of infrastructure and hydrological and weather conditions** can enhance their **operational efficiency**. Finally, authorities responsible for ensuring a smooth operation of inland waterway transport, such as the **Central Commission for the Navigation of the Rhine and the Danube Commission**, need a plethora of consistent information pertaining to various aspect of inland waterway operations, infrastructures, weather and hydrological conditions.

6.2 Countries and IWW corridors

The inland waterway market is locally constrained by the waterway inland waterway landscape, rendering certain countries more prominent potential markets for PLOTO solutions than others. According to Eurostat (Figure 5), the European **countries most actively involved in the IWT market** are The **Netherlands, Germany, Belgium and France**, followed by **Romania and Bulgaria**. Other countries participating in the market are **Austria, Hungary, Luxemburg, Slovakia, Croatia, Sweden, Poland, Finland and Czechia**. Figure 5 demonstrates the amount of transported goods transported (in thousands of tonnes) for 2022 according to the nationality and coverage of transporting vessels. **The more active a country is in inland waterway transportation, the more it can benefit from the solutions developed by PLOTO**. In that respect, **The Netherlands and Germany stand out**.

⁴ Latest Eurostat figures for the number of enterprises [sbs_na_1a_se_r2] are available for the year 2020

⁵ <https://www.mordorintelligence.com/industry-reports/europe-inland-water-freight-transport-market/companies>

Figure 5: Inland waterway transport by nationality of vessel and coverage for 2022, Unit of measure: Thousand tonnes, Nationality of registration of vessel: All countries of the world, Transport coverage: Total transport, Source: Eurostat

• Rhine

The IWW corridor of the **Rhine** extends from **Basel to the North Sea** and is usually considered in two parts, namely the Traditional Rhine area extending from Basel to the German-Dutch border and the Rhine Delta in the Netherlands extending from the German-Dutch border to the North Sea. The countries crossed by the Rhine are **Netherlands, Belgium, Germany, France and Luxembourg**. According to the CCNR Market Observation - Annual report 2023, **cargo transport** on the **Traditional Rhine** amounted to **155.5 million tonnes in 2022**, compared to **168.6 million tonnes in 2021** demonstrating a **7.8 % decrease**. As of the **Rhine delta area**, cargo transport in 2022 amounted to **237.8 million tonnes in 2022 compared to 254.6 million tonnes in 2021**, leading to a 6.6% decrease. Coal transport serves as a striking exception to these negative trends, as it increased by approximately 10.6 % from 2021 to 2022. It is important to mention that transport activity is not equally present along the Rhine. In particular, activity is **highest on the Lower Rhine compared to the Middle and Upper Rhine**. This is so because of the presence of the **Dutch Delta** area featuring considerable **petroleum and chemical industrial hubs** as well as a **high number of container terminals**. Moreover, the Lower Rhine region in Germany is an important steel and petroleum industrial hub and its high fairway depths facilitate transport operations.

- **Danube**

Transport via the Danube occurs **between Kelheim in Germany and the Black Sea via the Danube-Black Sea Canal and the Sulina Canal**. The main countries crossed by the Danube are: **Romania, and Hungary** followed by Croatia, Hungary, Slovakia and Austria. As in the case of the Rhine, traffic intensity is not equally distributed across the Danube. In particular, the **high-water depths in the lower Danube section**, the Danube delta region known as ‘maritime Danube’ allow for higher values in cargo transportation than upstream regions. **Between 2021 and 2022**, there was a **decrease of 20% in cargo transport performance**. Interestingly, transport via the Sulina Canal, which flows into the Black Sea in the Danube Delta area near the Romanian-Ukrainian border, more than **doubled between 2021 and 2022, going from 5.1 million tonnes in 2021 to 10.6 million tonnes in 2022**. The documented increase resulted from the need to find alternative routes for the Ukrainian exports of grain. It should be noted that the **Rhine outperforms the Danube** in terms of transportation volumes. For instance, container transport in **2022** for **Hungary amounted to 9000 tones and for Romania 190000 tonnes** while for **The Netherlands in was 45.6 million tonnes, for Belgium it was 19.0 million tonnes, for Germany 18.3 million tonnes and for France 3.5 million tonnes**.

6.3 Freight transport and handling

Inland waterways offer an efficient transportation alternative for all sorts of products. Agricultural, feedstuff and other food products constitute a prevalent type of dry cargo for IWW vessels. Other types of **dry cargo** are **iron ore, steel and metals, sand, stones, gravel, and other building materials**. As per liquid cargo, chemicals and petroleum products are often transported via IWW. Finally, containers are a prominent type of cargo.

Cargo transport through the **Rhine** plummeted during the period 2021-2022, with one considerable exception being coal which increased by 10.6%. As for the rest of the product segments: sand, stones and gravel decreased by 12.1%, containers decreased by 11.1%, mineral oil products decreased by 9.5% and metals decreased by 7.5%. Moreover, agri-food products transportation decreased by 5.9% while iron ore decreased by 2.8% and chemicals by 1.6%.

Cargo transport through the **Danube**, the Russian-Ukrainian war in 2022 hit hard IWW transportation for all types of products. As a result, in 2022, volumes of transport decreased for all cargo segments. Grain and other agricultural bulk lost 80% in transported volume on the Middle Danube while other food products and feedstuff lost 90% in transported volume.

6.4 Passenger transport

River cruise fleet in **Europe amounts for more than 40% of the world’s active river cruise fleet** and 75% of the total river cruise fleet in Europe is operating in central European waterways. For the **2022, 410 vessels are active** in the European area. The 2022 trends regarding this type of passenger transportation were quite promising. Indicatively, in **Germany** there was an **increase of 75% in the number of passengers booking a river cruise**. It should be noted that, although their original purpose was passenger transportation, the Russian-Ukrainian armed conflicted has given them an additional functionality, that or **floating hotels for refugees**.

6.5 Waste and renewable energy transport

The contribution of inland waterways in the promotion of **circular economy** is significant. The inland waterways offer an efficient way of transportation of **scrap steel, metal waste and iron waste**. In **London**, waste is collected from four riverside stations (Wandsworth, Battersea, City of London and Tower Hamlets) and subsequently transferred to an 'Energy from waste (EfW)' facility. The company responsible for the process, Cory Environmental⁶ reported that **731000 tonnes of non-recyclable waste** was transferred to its EfW facility in 2020. This is the only EfW facility in the UK with river infrastructure for that purpose. In **Paris**, the **Seine** facilitates transport of **household waste**. The waste is transported by the public service company SYCTOM. According to their 2020 activity report, **189.7 thousand tonnes of waste** were transported, 92.4% was recycled. An interesting alternative use of inland waterways in France, was reported in Lyon, **where floating boats are used as waste disposal centres**, in an effort to overcome space scarcity in urban areas.

The most important sources of renewable electricity generation are: **wind, solar photovoltaics, biogases, geothermal, hydropower and primary solid biomass**. The Inland waterway transport market can claim an important role in the energy transition. This is due to the **large loading capacity of inland vessels**. The most prominent cases of **renewable energy transportation** are: **wind turbines, biomass and biofuel and hydrogen**.

6.6 Market trends

According to simulations run for the purposes of the Assessment of potential of maritime and inland ports and inland waterways (European Commission, 2020), over the period **2000-2014 the growth rate of IWT container traffic amounted to 5% per year on average**. The pandemic and the Russian war combined with a low water period had a negative impact on IWT freight transportation. According to the CCNR Market Insight for April 2023, a **decrease of 2.8% in European inland waterway transport** performance, especially in the Danube area, was registered for the first half of 2022 compared to the respective period in 2021. A positive exception is **coal transport**, which was **increased by 25.7% in 2022**. As per the size of the inland water freight transport industry, a CAGR of over 5% is anticipated for the period 2024-2029, with Europe being the fastest growing market.⁶

6.7 Current relevant operating challenges

Adverse hydrological conditions

The **low water period in July and August 2022** and the even worse **draught of 2018** is one example of the adverse hydrological conditions that obstruct inland waterway transport and need to be monitored closely. Water levels influence the **load factor of the vessel**, which is the **ratio of cargo loaded to the loading capacity of the vessel**, and therefore the overall **profitability of inland waterway transport**.

Inland waterway infrastructures

According to the OECD, inland waterway infrastructures are defined as follows: **Infrastructure includes land, channels and permanent way constructions, buildings, navigation locks, mooring equipment,**

⁶ <https://www.mordorintelligence.com/industry-reports/europe-inland-water-freight-transport-market/market-size>

toll collection installations, as well as immovable fixtures, fittings and installations connected with them (signalisation, telecommunications, etc.) as opposed to IWT vessels⁷.

- **Non-comparability of data collection methods regarding the state of IWW infrastructure**

Monitoring IWW infrastructures is crucial, however the data collection system is fragmented and varies from country to country, not allowing for a more centralised strategic development.

- **Limited investment in technological upgrade of the IWW**

Investments in IWW infrastructures focus on the maintenance of existing facilities and their extension or replacement with more technologically advanced and efficient ones.

⁷ <https://stats.oecd.org/glossary/detail.asp?ID=3957>

7 PLOTO – positioning in the market

7.1 Solutions – Challenge mitigation tools

In response to the pre-stated operating challenges in IWT pertaining to the technological upgrade and integration of IWW infrastructures, PLOTO offers mitigation technological tools along the following lines (Figure 6):

Figure 6: PLOTO solution categories

7.2 PLOTO Competition landscape

Competition for PLOTO operates along two main services: vulnerability modelling and damage assessment. Since PLOTO is an ongoing research project with market potential, we are interested in final products that are already in the market and serve similar purposes as well as projects under development which could serve as future competition for the Key Exploitable Results developed under PLOTO. The focus is placed on European competition for multi-hazard and vulnerability modelling. In particular, KER2: **Fast assessment damage maps (satellite, ground sensor and UAV- based)** faces the highest competition. Companies such as: AceCore Technologies, Aerialtronics, Aeroscout, AiDrones, Alpha Unmanned Systems, Altavian, Arcturus-UAV, Baykar Machine, COBHAM, Delft Dynamics, DJI Innovations, ERA, Flightech Systems, High Eye, Indela, Innocon, Italdron, Laflamme Aero, Latitude Engineering, MavTech, MERIO, MikroKopter, R4 Robotics, Shandong LongYi Aviation Technology, Steadicopter, Sunbirds, Swift Radioplanes, Threed Systems, UAV Solutions and UAVision develop systems with technical characteristics that serve the purpose of fast and efficient damage assessment. PLOTO's main advantage over the competition is based on the **provision of an integrated solution** including data fusion services, weather predictions tools, risk and socioeconomic impact assessment. Finally, it should be noted that competitor identification is a work in progress and as the project and relevant technologies evolve, new competitors for PLOTO are expected to arise.

7.2.1 Research products

A framework for systemic risk evaluation of inland waterway infrastructure

In a recent publication in the Progress in Disaster Science Journal, a framework for systemic risk evaluation of inland waterway infrastructure is presented by researchers affiliated with the Karlsruhe Institute for Technology and the Technical University Freiberg in Germany (Wehrle et al., 2022). Based on a **GIS-based risk-dashboard**, the framework allows for a **holistic assessment of the inland waterway infrastructure**. Their **systems-of-systems modelling approach** implicates critical subsystems such as buildings, networks, industries and populations. The goal of the tool is to facilitate decision-making with respect to waterway infrastructure by projecting the impact of its deterioration on power and water supply. In particular, the tool demonstrates the **interdependencies between the implicated subsystems** and the **associated risk interlinkages** with an **Input-Output Model** while providing a realistic account of the spatial dimension via a GIS-based decision tool.

ReNEW

ReNEW is a **HORIZON funded project** aiming at developing solutions that will enhance the **climate-neutrality and climate-resilience of IWT**. Implicating 24 partners from 11 countries, ReNEW is a 3-year long project aims to deliver an interdisciplinary **IWT Resilience and Sustainability decision-support framework** to enhance targeted and **innovative infrastructure resilience and sustainability** solutions. Moreover, a **Green Resilient IWT Dataspace** coupled with a generic **Digital Twin** will be delivered. The developments of the project are being tested in four living labs including the Ghent and Douro waterways.

8 Roadmap to market and business modelling methodology and tools

8.1 PESTLE analysis

8.1.1 PLOTTO project PESTLE analysis

A PESTLE analysis is a framework used to evaluate the macro-environmental factors that may impact an entity. It stands for Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal, and Environmental factors.

The PESTLE analysis of inland navigation in Europe reveals its multifaceted nature, influenced by political, economic, social, technological, legal, and environmental factors. Understanding these factors is essential for comprehensively assessing the landscape of inland navigation and formulating strategies for its sustainable development.

Integrating inland waterway transport in the intermodal supply chain has been recognized as crucial for enhancing service performance (Caris et al., 2014). Additionally, research has shown that inland navigation can be utilized for various segments of urban freight transport, highlighting its potential role in city logistics (Janjevic & Ndiaye, 2014). Furthermore, inland navigation has been demonstrated to be a viable alternative for road transport in urban areas, indicating its potential to improve efficiency in freight transport (Durajczyk & Drop, 2021).

From a political perspective, the modernization of inland waterways is crucial for inland waterway transport, including the introduction of traffic control systems and renovation/modernization works of hydrotechnical structures (Jerzyło & Wawrzyńska, 2018). Additionally, the development of inland ports along waterways has emerged as a solution to space limitations and congestion in port areas, enhancing the reliability of connections and expanding the geographical scope, particularly in northern Europe (Roso et al., 2020).

Economically, the resilience and optimization techniques applied to inland waterway networks are vital for the flow of commodities essential for the more extensive multimodal transportation network (Baroud et al., 2014). Furthermore, the economic viability of inland waterways is closely related to improving infrastructure, energy consumption, and vessel carrying capacity (Szaruga & Załoga, 2022). Additionally, the potential of inland navigation has been highlighted, with measurable benefits and possibilities of use indicating its economic significance (Kaup et al., 2022). In addition, the role of inland waterway transport in Serbia's economic development has been studied, emphasizing its economic impact (Milanković et al., 2018). Furthermore, the lower freight rates and lower biomass consumption characteristic of riverine trade have been identified as contributing to economic growth and regional specialization, underscoring the economic importance of inland waterways (Moreno & Moreno-Álvarez, 2022).

From a social perspective, the prospects of waterway development can significantly impact regional and community socioeconomic levels, making it essential to initiate specific studies on the feasibility of inland waterways in terms of technicality, environmental impact, social development, and economic development (Yassin et al., 2010). Moreover, the safety management of waterway congestions is crucial to addressing increasing waiting times at locks and inland ports due to traffic congestion, ensuring optimal use of available capacity (Yan et al., 2017).

Environmentally, the comparison of inland waterways regarding geographic and climatic conditions, water resources management practices, navigability, environmental problems, and socioeconomic conditions is particularly justified given climate change (Nemethy et al., 2022). Additionally, the environmental impacts of inland waterway transport, including noise levels and energy consumption, are critical considerations for environmental management (Dai et al., 2015; Dai et al., 2016).

From a legal perspective, the analysis of the theoretical and normative bases of inland navigation law in countries like Germany and Ukraine has been conducted, shedding light on the legal framework governing inland navigation (Мошак, 2022). Moreover, the European Commission has been actively promoting inland navigation, particularly for transporting goods from seaports to the hinterland, emphasizing the significance of legal and regulatory aspects in facilitating inland navigation (Zajíček & Wolter, 2019). Additionally, the legislative base of countries such as Ukraine plays a significant role in developing inland waterways, and proposals for improving the legislative base have been made to support this development (Stets et al., 2020). Furthermore, transporting dangerous goods along inland waterways requires a comprehensive risk assessment framework to calculate associated risks (Huang et al., 2021).

From a technological standpoint, the mechanization of inland navigation since the 19th century has facilitated the construction of significant navigation works, such as canals and inland waterways, indicating the technological advancements in this sector (Carse & Lewis, 2020). Moreover, the use of navigational simulators for training inland waterways navigators has been discussed, highlighting the technological advancements in training and safety measures for inland navigation (Prokhorenkov et al., 2020). The challenges posed by scenes of inland waterways, such as the complex distribution of obstacles, GPS signal denial environment, and fog over the water surface, impede the application of unmanned surface vehicles in inland waterways (Cheng et al., 2021). Additionally, the construction and application of digital twins for inland waterways combined with 3D video have been shown to improve safety management and emergency response (Wu et al., 2021).

Since the PLOTO project focuses on improving the resilience of Inland Waterways against climate change and other extremes, **a PESTLE is constructed taking into consideration the following aspects in each category** (political, economic, social, technological):

Political:

- The European Commission's transport infrastructure and sustainability policies could significantly influence inland waterway transport.
- Collaboration or agreements between European countries, particularly those that share waterways, would impact the development of inland navigation.
- Political stability in the European region, which facilitates investments in transport infrastructure and services, plays a critical role.

Economic:

- The overall economic climate of Europe, including GDP growth, trade volumes, and investment in infrastructure, affects Inland Waterways Transport (IWT).
- The competitive landscape, marked by the modal split between IWT, road, and rail transport, can shape the demand for inland navigation.
- Transport performance in terms of tonne-kilometres and revenue generated from goods and passenger transport influences the sector's economic viability.

Social:

- Public perception and acceptance of inland waterway transport can impact its development.
- The need for employment within the IWT sector and the professional competencies required will affect the social aspects of the industry.
- Using inland waterways for leisure and tourism also has social implications and affects the demand for passenger transport services.

Technological:

- Advancements in WebGIS technology are enhancing the management and safety of waterborne traffic, particularly in areas like the Three Gorges Reservoir.
- Developments in vessel technology, including automation and sustainable fuel usage, can improve efficiency and reduce environmental impact.
- Integrating information systems, river information services, and other technological advancements improves the efficiency and reliability of inland waterway transport.
- Technology can also enhance predictive maintenance of the waterways and the fleet, leading to lower operational costs and increased safety.

Legal:

- European directives and regulations that govern water quality, shipping safety, and pollution control directly affect the operations of IWT.
- International, national, and regional legislation concerning emissions, waste management, and vessel standards play a significant role in the legal context.
- Trade agreements and laws on tariffs and customs influence IWT by facilitating or constraining cross-border transportation.

Environmental:

- The ecological impact of inland navigation, including emissions and water pollution, must be continuously assessed and managed.
- Water level fluctuation due to climate change can have significant implications for the reliability and capacity of IWT.
- Efforts to enhance sustainability, such as clean propulsion technologies and green corridors, are integral to the environmental aspect of IWT.

Specifically, regarding the PLOTO Project itself, the PESTLE analysis is presented below:

Political:

- The project will likely be influenced by EU climate, infrastructure, and transportation policies.
- International cooperation and regulations within the EU member states could affect project operations and standards.
- The project's success may depend on support and commitments from political entities in Belgium, Romania, and Hungary, where case studies are set.

Economic:

- The European Climate, Infrastructure, and Environment Executive Agency funds the project, suggesting EU investment priorities.
- Outcomes might influence economic activities related to waterway logistics and transport.
- Economic factors like funding for climate change adaptation and the financial implications of extreme weather disrupting the transportation network may also be relevant.

Social:

- There is increasing public awareness and demand for climate change adaptation and resilient infrastructures.

- Changing societal attitudes might affect the acceptance and collaboration among the stakeholders impacted by IWW.
- Society's reliance on effective and resilient transport infrastructures for goods and services could drive support for the project.

Technological:

- Adopting cutting-edge technology, such as sensor-generated data, UAV and satellite observations, tailored weather forecasts, and machine learning for infrastructure assessment will be pivotal.
- Integration of advanced simulation tools and real-time data processing for managing IWW infrastructure effectively.
- Infrastructure improvements may include developing and using new materials or methods that are more durable and adaptable to climate impacts.

Legal:

- The project must comply with a range of EU legislation and standards relating to climate change, environmental protection, and transport safety.
- Intellectual property rights, such as trademarks or rights of partners in the exploitation of results, must be managed within the consortium undefined.
- Legal documents, such as Consortium Agreements, will outline data management and dissemination rules and IPR considerations undefined.

Environmental:

- The project is centered around improving resilience to environmental challenges, including the effects of climate change and extreme weather events on infrastructures.
- Efforts to reduce the environmental footprint, promote sustainability, and mitigate impacts such as habitat fragmentation and biodiversity degradation are crucial and undefined.
- Solutions are being developed to limit vulnerability to disruptions while minimizing negative environmental impacts and enhancing eco-friendly transport modalities undefined.

The PESTLE analysis of inland navigation in Europe, particularly within the context of the PLOTO project, reveals a complex interplay of political, economic, social, technological, legal, and environmental factors. These factors shape the industry's resilience and capacity to adapt to challenges such as climate change. Collaborative efforts among EU nations, advancements in technology, and legal frameworks play crucial roles in enhancing the sustainability and efficiency of inland waterways. Economic considerations, including investment in infrastructure and the competitive landscape, influence the sector's viability. Social acceptance and environmental considerations, including the impact on climate and resource management, are pivotal for future development. This comprehensive analysis underscores the need for integrated strategies that leverage technological innovations, foster international cooperation, and prioritize sustainable practices to ensure the resilience and growth of inland navigation amidst evolving global challenges.

8.1.2 PESTLE analysis per KER

8.1.2.1 Fast assessment damage maps (satellite, ground sensor and UAV- based)

Political:

- The implementation and usage of such technology could be influenced by government policies related to emergency management, data privacy, and UAV regulations.

- Collaborations with government agencies, as suggested in the SWOT analysis, indicate a need to align with political and regulatory frameworks.

Economic:

- The cost structure involved in satellite and UAV operations, sensor maintenance, and data processing infrastructure could be significant.
- The revenue streams from selling assessments, subscription models, and customized analysis services would need to be balanced against these costs.

Social:

- The system's ability to provide fast, accurate, and comprehensive damage assessments can significantly impact disaster response and recovery efforts, potentially saving lives and reducing economic losses.
- Public acceptance and trust in technology play a crucial role.

Technological:

- The integration of satellite, UAV-based, and ground sensor technologies, along with advanced data processing and analysis, is central to this innovation.
- Rapid advancements in these areas could both offer opportunities and pose threats of obsolescence.

Legal:

- Compliance with laws and regulations related to UAV flights, data collection, and privacy, especially in different jurisdictions, would be crucial for the deployment of this technology.

Environmental:

- The application of this technology in environmental monitoring and early detection of hazards like forest fires, floods, and landslides aligns with global efforts to mitigate environmental risks and manage natural disasters more effectively.

8.1.2.2 Middleware and Data Fusion Services

Strengths:

- Integration and processing of data from various sources, providing fast and easy access to a wealth of pre-processed data relevant to specific application domains, thereby increasing the efficiency and accuracy of the information provided.

Weaknesses:

- Inland Waterway (IWW) end-users may not be particularly interested in sophisticated Information and Communication Technology (ICT) solutions, especially given the current level of economic crisis. Additionally, the existence of easy-to-use and user-friendly platforms, along with the rapid technical evolution in the domain, may deter end-users due to fears of quick obsolescence.

Opportunities:

- IWW organizations may need to upgrade existing systems and services to meet European Commission (EC) standards and global trends in the specific domain, making them more resilient and adaptive to climate change. This presents a significant opportunity for adopting Middleware and Data Fusion Services.

Threats:

- Intense competition from US and Asian-based competitors in the industrial bot market, heterogeneous legislation and policies per country, and significant differences in country development, size, and number of utilities contribute to a local and non-homogeneous European market, posing market entry and expansion challenges.

8.1.2.3 Fore-Now/Casting Weather Predictions tool.

Strengths:

- Integrates high-end, high-resolution modeling techniques focused on the very local scale, covering critical infrastructure areas of interest, and operational mesoscale modeling techniques capable of covering extended areas around the target field sites.
- Flexible system that can be easily adjusted for harmonization with other existing technologies and platforms.

Weaknesses:

- IWW end-users might not be particularly interested in sophisticated modeling solutions due to the current level of economic crisis and a lack of understanding of what the generated modeling data represent.
- System operation and maintenance require highly skilled and trained staff, with potential reliability issues related to maintenance, such as power surges or sensor transmission failures.

Opportunities:

- Successful implementation could apply to other fields such as utilities and emerging markets in developing countries with funding for similar projects.
- Potential to open up markets in the US and Asia through international partnerships.

Threats:

- Existence of equally strong competitors, mainly from the US and East Asia in terms of the scientific knowledge needed for system development.
- Risk of big worldwide companies seeking to suppress initiatives in this field, usually driven mostly by SMEs.
- Competition from low-cost IWW-oriented platforms

8.1.2.4 Integrated PLOT platform

Strengths:

- The platform integrates high technology with easy implementation within existing systems and facilities, showing a strong capacity to harmonize with other technologies and platforms.

Weaknesses:

- There's a potential lack of interest from IWW end-users in sophisticated ICT solutions, mainly due to the current economic crisis. Additionally, the need for special training for platform operators could be seen as a barrier to adoption.

Opportunities:

- There's potential for successful implementation in other applications beyond the initial scope, such as utilities, and emerging markets in developing countries with funding for similar projects. The platform may also open up US and Asian markets through international partnerships.

Threats:

- There is strong competition from the US, and Asian-based competitors are already established in the market. The initiatives driven mainly through smaller players (SMEs) in Europe may face challenges from big worldwide players. Additionally, there's competition from low-cost IWW-oriented platforms.

8.1.2.5 Risk Assessment Engine

Strengths:

- Developing a comprehensive risk assessment framework and modelling framework for assessing impacts between interconnected IWW sites/elements enhances the safety and optimization of complex infrastructures.
- Solutions focus on risk modelling, identification, prediction, improvement, and optimization related to operational processes and interactions inside and outside the infrastructures.

Weaknesses:

- The software requires specialized analyses to generate input data, making it of a general nature but necessitating significant customization for each client or case study.
- Potential reluctance from end-users to provide detailed information about assets at risk.
- Simplifications are needed for application to large areas such as IWW and urban regions.

Opportunities:

- Possible applicability to other areas, such as the impact of climate change on critical infrastructure opening up emerging markets.

Threats:

- Competition from large private companies and reputable universities in the EU, US, and Asia, already established in the field.
- The presence of other competitive technologies, products, or solutions, especially in the domain of catastrophe modelling

8.1.2.6 Software for assessing socioeconomic impact.

Strengths:

- Supports the resilience of Inland Waterway Transportation (IWW).
- Provides a socioeconomic model of residents, IWW-related economy (transportation of goods, services), small businesses, and local governance, offering a hierarchical model of the function of the IWW-related community.
- Can be extended to other applications related to risk and resilience assessment, such as highways, urban areas, and cultural heritage.

Weaknesses:

- Requires specialized datasets provided by end-users.
- Needs modifications for applications other than IWW.

Opportunities:

- Successful implementation can be applied to many other applications, such as the effect of climate change on critical infrastructure and emerging markets.

Threats:

- Competition from prominent US and Asia-based private companies already working in the field.
- Other competitive technologies, products, or solutions from US and Asia-based private companies and centers of excellence.

8.2 SWOT analysis

8.2.1 PLOTTO project SWOT analysis

The literature provides a comprehensive overview of inland navigation in Europe, including its potential, challenges, safety concerns, environmental impacts, and operational considerations. This information is crucial for conducting a SWOT analysis to assess the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats associated with inland navigation in Europe.

Inland navigation in Europe presents opportunities and challenges, as evidenced by the literature. The European inland navigation industry can potentially increase its role in creating more efficient and sustainable logistic chains (Preuß et al., 2023). Inland navigation can improve supply chain service performance (Caris et al., 2014). Furthermore, inland navigation networks cover more than 37,000 kilometers in Europe, highlighting the extensive reach of this mode of transport (Segovia et al., 2017). However, there are also challenges associated with inland navigation. For instance, the expansion of European waterways within EC projects like TEN-T and NAIADES requires consideration in river restoration programs to mitigate the effects of navigation on riverine habitats (Kucera-Hirzinger et al., 2008; Flores et al., 2021). Additionally, inland navigation contributes to remobilizing land-based plastics into riverine systems, indicating potential environmental impacts (Climo et al., 2022).

Moreover, the safety of navigation on inland waterways has been a topic of concern, with initiatives such as establishing a safety committee for inland navigation vessels by PIANC and issuing recommendations by UNECE (Ghesmi & Moctar, 2019). The reliability of delivery by inland shipping is affected by navigation closed periods when deliveries are not made, highlighting operational challenges (Kotowska et al., 2020). Additionally, the effects of recreational and commercial navigation on fish assemblages in large rivers have been studied, indicating potential ecological impacts (Zajíček & Wolter, 2019).

An additional SWOT analysis can be conducted to enhance the resilience of inland waterways in Europe against climate change and other extremes. Several studies provide valuable insights into this topic. Baroud et al. (2014) emphasize the importance of quantifying the resilience of inland waterway networks, particularly concerning commodity flows. They highlight the lack of published work in this area, indicating a potential weakness in the current understanding of network resilience. Additionally, Schoeneich et al. (2022) demonstrate the potential for reducing CO₂ emissions through the development of inland transport, presenting an opportunity for environmental improvement.

Furthermore, Pant et al. (2015) draw attention to the susceptibility of inland ports to natural climate impacts and accidental failures, indicating a weakness in the resilience of the current infrastructure. Durajczyk & Drop (2021) stress the need for investments in revitalizing and upgrading linear waterway infrastructure, highlighting a potential weakness in the current state of infrastructure. Additionally, Kaup et al. (2022) emphasize the impact of climatic conditions on the navigability of inland waterways, representing a threat to the efficiency of this mode of transport.

Moreover, Guan et al. (2021) underscores the importance of optimizing lock operations to improve the efficiency of inland waterway transport, indicating an opportunity for operational enhancement. Jerzyło & Wawrzyńska (2018) advocate for the modernization of inland waterways to introduce traffic

control systems and unify navigational marking systems, presenting an opportunity for infrastructure improvement. Stets et al. (2020) highlight the potential for Ukraine to learn from the experience of European Union countries in enhancing the use of inland waterways, representing an opportunity for knowledge transfer and improvement.

In particular, regarding the PLOTO Project itself, the SWOT analysis is presented below:

Strengths:

- Involvement of major players across various fields, including transport infrastructures, industry, SMEs, and academic partners.
- High-tech solutions with the capacity to integrate effortlessly within existing systems.
- The capacity of PLOTO to harmonize with other technologies and platforms.
- Innovative integration of new technologies and potential applicability to various applications beyond IWW, like utilities.

Weaknesses:

- Potential lack of interest from IWW end-users in sophisticated ICT solutions, particularly during economic downturns.
- Need for special training for system operators, potentially contributing to resistance to adopting new technologies.
- Possibility of technical obsolescence due to rapid technological evolution.
- The diversity of stakeholders involved can lead to difficulties in collaboration due to PLOTO's multidisciplinary approach.

Opportunities:

- Emerging markets in developing countries provide new funding avenues for infrastructure projects.
- The opportunity to expand into US and Asian markets through international partnerships.
- The fundamental necessity to upgrade existing services to meet EC standards and global trends.
- Technological advancements could lead to more efficient monitoring and projections, thus mitigating economic losses from disruptions in river navigation.

Threats:

- Intense competition from existing US and Asian players, especially in the industrial bot market.
- Big players worldwide potentially dominate the market, possibly overshadowing European SME initiatives.
- Heterogeneous legislation and policies across countries create a complex legal environment for implementation.
- Competition from low-cost IWW-oriented management tools.

Furthermore, a SWOT analysis for PLOTO's Key Exploitable Results should categorize the internal strengths and weaknesses of the KERs, as well as the external opportunities and threats facing them in the market or deployment context. Here's a SWOT analysis for KERs, based on their characteristics:

Strengths:

- Innovation Level: The KERs represent novel solutions or significant improvements over existing technologies or services, which can give a competitive edge.
- Technical Excellence: Advanced technical features, reliability, or performance that exceed industry standards.

- **Cost Efficiency:** KERs offer cost savings to users or customers by lowering initial costs or reducing long-term operating expenses.

Weaknesses:

- **Development Stage:** If the KERs are not yet fully developed, this can be a weakness as it may delay market entry or require additional investments.
- **Complexity:** A highly complex KER might face user adoption challenges or require extensive training for users to benefit fully.
- **Resource Constraints:** Limitations in workforce, finances, or technology can hinder further development or scaling of the KERs.

Opportunities:

- **Market Trends:** Existing trends in the market that align with the capabilities or purposes of the KERs can represent significant opportunities.
- **Partnerships:** Potential collaborations with other entities can offer joint development, marketing, or distribution opportunities.
- **Regulatory Environment:** A favorable regulatory scenario that encourages the adoption of new technologies or services represented by the KERs.

Threats:

- **Competition:** Established competitors or new entrants with similar offerings can threaten the success of KERs.
- **Technological Obsolescence:** The rapid pace of technology could lead to the KERs becoming outdated quickly if continuous innovation is not maintained.
- **Economic Factors:** Broader economic factors can affect customer purchasing power and investment in new technologies, which could threaten the commercial viability of the KERs.

The SWOT analysis for the PLOTO Project within the context of inland navigation in Europe reveals a strategic framework for understanding its internal strengths and weaknesses, as well as external opportunities and threats. The project's strengths lie in its collaborative approach, involving key stakeholders from various sectors and the integration of high-tech solutions, which are easily adaptable to existing systems and have the potential for broader applications beyond inland waterways. However, challenges such as potential disinterest from end-users in sophisticated ICT solutions, the need for specialized training, and the risk of technological obsolescence highlight the project's vulnerabilities.

Opportunities for the PLOTO Project emerge from emerging markets in developing countries and the potential for expansion into US and Asian markets through international partnerships, along with the necessity to upgrade services to meet European Commission standards and global trends. Technological advancements present further opportunities to enhance monitoring and mitigate economic losses due to disruptions in navigation.

Conversely, the project faces threats from intense competition, particularly from established players in the US and Asia, and the complexity of heterogeneous legislation and policies across different countries, which could complicate implementation. Additionally, there's the challenge of competing against low-cost management tools targeted at inland waterway navigation.

The analysis underscores the importance of leveraging the PLOTO Project's strengths and opportunities to overcome its weaknesses and navigate the threats it faces. Success will likely hinge on strategic partnerships, continuous innovation, and the ability to adapt to the evolving regulatory and competitive landscape.

8.2.2 SWOT analysis per KER

8.2.2.1 Fast assessment damage maps (satellite, ground sensor and UAV- based)

Strengths:

- **Rapid Response:** Enables quick assessment of damages post-disaster, crucial for timely and effective response and relief efforts.
- **Comprehensive Coverage:** Integrates data from satellites, ground sensors, and UAVs, offering a broad and detailed perspective of affected areas.
- **High Accuracy:** Advanced technologies and data integration can provide high-resolution and accurate damage assessments, essential for precise resource allocation.
- **Cost-Effective:** Potentially reduces the cost and time involved in damage assessment by leveraging automated processes and remote sensing technologies.

Weaknesses:

- **Technical Complexity:** The integration of various data sources and technologies can be complex, requiring specialized expertise for operation and interpretation.
- **Dependence on Technology:** Relies heavily on the availability and functioning of sophisticated equipment and technologies, which can be disrupted in disaster scenarios.
- **Data Overload:** The vast amount of data generated can be overwhelming to process and analyze, particularly in a rapid response context.
- **Accessibility Issues:** In some regions, especially remote or underdeveloped areas, the required technological infrastructure may be lacking or inadequate.

Opportunities:

- **Technological Advancements:** Continuous improvements in sensor technology, satellite imagery, and UAV capabilities can enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of damage assessments.
- **Integration with Emergency Management Systems:** Can be integrated into broader emergency management and disaster response frameworks, improving overall disaster resilience.
- **Collaborations:** Opportunities for partnerships with governmental agencies, NGOs, and private entities involved in disaster management and humanitarian aid.
- **Expansion of Use Cases:** Beyond disaster response, the technology can be adapted for use in urban planning, environmental monitoring, and infrastructure management.

Threats:

- **Cybersecurity Risks:** The reliance on digital technologies and data transmission exposes the system to potential cybersecurity threats, which could compromise data integrity and privacy.
- **Funding and Resource Constraints:** Sustained investment is required for the development, maintenance, and operation of such systems, which might be challenging in resource-limited settings.
- **Regulatory and Legal Challenges:** The use of UAVs and the collection of data through various means may face regulatory hurdles and privacy concerns, especially across different jurisdictions.

- Environmental and Operational Limitations: Extreme weather conditions and challenging terrains can limit the operation of UAVs and the effectiveness of ground sensors and satellites.

8.2.2.2 Middleware and Data Fusion Services

Strengths:

- Integration and processing of data from various sources, providing fast and easy access to a wealth of pre-processed data relevant to specific application domains, thereby increasing the efficiency and accuracy of the information provided.

Weaknesses:

- Inland Waterway (IWW) end-users may not be particularly interested in sophisticated Information and Communication Technology (ICT) solutions, especially given the current level of economic crisis. Additionally, the existence of easy-to-use and user-friendly platforms, along with the rapid technical evolution in the domain, may deter end-users due to fears of quick obsolescence.

Opportunities:

- IWW organizations may need to upgrade existing systems and services to meet European Commission (EC) standards and global trends in the specific domain, making them more resilient and adaptive to climate change. This presents a significant opportunity for adopting Middleware and Data Fusion Services.

Threats:

- Intense competition from US and Asian-based competitors in the industrial bot market, heterogeneous legislation and policies per country, and significant differences in country development, size, and number of utilities contribute to a local and non-homogeneous European market, posing market entry and expansion challenges.

8.2.2.3 Fore-Now/Casting Weather Predictions tool.

Strengths:

- Integrates high-end, high-resolution modeling techniques focused on the very local scale, covering critical infrastructure areas of interest, and operational mesoscale modeling techniques capable of covering extended areas around the target field sites.
- Flexible system that can be easily adjusted for harmonization with other existing technologies and platforms.

Weaknesses:

- IWW end-users might not be particularly interested in sophisticated modeling solutions due to the current level of economic crisis and a lack of understanding of what the generated modeling data represent.
- System operation and maintenance require highly skilled and trained staff, with potential reliability issues related to maintenance, such as power surges or sensor transmission failures.

Opportunities:

- Successful implementation could apply to other fields such as utilities and emerging markets in developing countries with funding for similar projects.
- Potential to open up markets in the US and Asia through international partnerships.

Threats:

- Existence of equally strong competitors, mainly from the US and East Asia in terms of the scientific knowledge needed for system development.
- Risk of big worldwide companies seeking to suppress initiatives in this field, usually driven mostly by SMEs.
- Competition from low-cost IWW-oriented platforms

8.2.2.4 Integrated PLOTTO platform

Strengths:

- The platform integrates high technology with easy implementation within existing systems and facilities, showing a strong capacity to harmonize with other technologies and platforms.

Weaknesses:

- There's a potential lack of interest from IWW end-users in sophisticated ICT solutions, mainly due to the current economic crisis. Additionally, the need for special training for platform operators could be seen as a barrier to adoption.

Opportunities:

- There's potential for successful implementation in other applications beyond the initial scope, such as utilities, and emerging markets in developing countries with funding for similar projects. The platform may also open up US and Asian markets through international partnerships.

Threats:

- There is strong competition from the US, and Asian-based competitors are already established in the market. The initiatives driven mainly through smaller players (SMEs) in Europe may face challenges from big worldwide players. Additionally, there's competition from low-cost IWW-oriented platforms.

8.2.2.5 Risk Assessment Engine

Strengths:

- Developing a comprehensive risk assessment framework and modelling framework for assessing impacts between interconnected IWW sites/elements enhances the safety and optimization of complex infrastructures.
- Solutions focus on risk modelling, identification, prediction, improvement, and optimization related to operational processes and interactions inside and outside the infrastructures.

Weaknesses:

- The software requires specialized analyses to generate input data, making it of a general nature but necessitating significant customization for each client or case study.
- Potential reluctance from end-users to provide detailed information about assets at risk.
- Simplifications are needed for application to large areas such as IWW and urban regions.

Opportunities:

- Possible applicability to other areas, such as the impact of climate change on critical infrastructure opening up emerging markets.

Threats:

- Competition from large private companies and reputable universities in the EU, US, and Asia, already established in the field.
- The presence of other competitive technologies, products, or solutions, especially in the domain of catastrophe modelling

8.2.2.6 Software for assessing socioeconomic impact

Strengths:

- Supports the resilience of Inland Waterway Transportation (IWW).
- Provides a socioeconomic model of residents, IWW-related economy (transportation of goods, services), small businesses, and local governance, offering a hierarchical model of the function of the IWW-related community.
- Can be extended to other applications related to risk and resilience assessment, such as highways, urban areas, and cultural heritage.

Weaknesses:

- Requires specialized datasets provided by end-users.
- Needs modifications for applications other than IWW.

Opportunities:

- Successful implementation can be applied to many other applications, such as the effect of climate change on critical infrastructure and emerging markets.

Threats:

- Competition from prominent US and Asia-based private companies already working in the field.
- Other competitive technologies, products, or solutions from US and Asia-based private companies and centers of excellence.

8.3 Business Model Canvas (BMC)

8.3.1 PLOTTO project BMC

The Business Model Canvas (BMC) is a widely used tool for visualizing, assessing, and developing business models. It provides a flexible template for conceiving, completing, and evaluating business models. The BMC analysis has been utilized in various contexts, such as business development strategies, teaching entrepreneurship, and analysing specific business models. Additionally, the BMC has been extended and adapted to incorporate service logic principles better and drive venture success. It has also been applied in the context of sustainability, energy enterprises, and micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs).

Furthermore, the BMC has been used in analysing lean manufacturing strategies, platform businesses, and e-business startups. The BMC has been employed in various industries, including tourism, food service, and digital wallet implementation. Moreover, it has been compared with Lean Canvas and utilized in startup business methods and language learning startups.

Using the BMC approach mentioned, here is a conceptual Business Model Canvas for the PLOTTO project:

1. Key Partners:

- Various academic institutions, technological companies, and industry partners involved in the project are undefined.
- NETCOMPANY - INTRASOFT (Coordinator)
- Other beneficiaries including EXUS, BME, UM, DBC, RSOE, ULIEGE, AFDJ, UDG, RRT, MAV, NTUA, RISA, BSZL, FMI, SoReCC, SPW MI, AUTH, ERTC, STWS
- European Commission as the funding body.
- End-users such as IWW operators, maintenance teams, and first response units for transport infrastructures.

2. Key Activities:

- Research and development activities to advance the state-of-the-art in IWW resilience.
- Increasing resilience of Inland Waterways (IWW) infrastructures.
- Combining climate change scenarios with simulation tools.
- Developing integrated tools for infrastructure management.
- Integration of multi-sensor and satellite-based data.
- Development of decision support systems and a common operational picture.
- Validation and demonstration activities in different case studies.

3. Key Resources:

- High-resolution modeling data.
- Sensor-generated data (including computer vision).
- Multi-temporal, multi-sensor UAV- and satellite-based observations.
- Intellectual capital from research institutions and industry experts.
- Technologies for UAV inspection, atmospheric impact assessment, and decision support systems.
- Financial resources from the European Commission and project partners.

4. Value Propositions:

- Enhanced resilience of Inland Waterways infrastructure.
- Integrated tools for effective infrastructure management under a variety of conditions.
- Common Operational Picture with enhanced visualization and Incident Management System.
- Reduced costs and improved efficiency for IWW operators.

5. Customer Relationships:

- Long-term partnerships with IWW operators and transport infrastructure companies.
- Customer service and technical support for the technologies developed.
- Training and workshops for end-users.

6. Channels:

- Direct sales to IWW operators and associated stakeholders.
- Marketing via professional conferences, industry publications, and online platforms.
- Demonstrations and case studies showcasing the benefits of the PLOTO project.

7. Customer Segments:

- IWW infrastructure operators and maintenance teams.
- Authorities and first response units for emergency planning.
- Research institutions and companies in the field of transport infrastructure inspection and maintenance.

8. Cost Structure:

- Costs related to R&D and the integration of innovative technologies.
- Expenses for managing the consortium, such as meeting coordination and communication with the European Commission.
- Costs associated with the dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities of the project results.

9. Revenue Streams:

- Contracts with infrastructural operators for using the PLOTO system and associated maintenance services.
- Licensing agreements for software and technologies developed within the project.
- The potential for monetizing the solutions via adaptation for other related sectors and spin-off products.

The Business Model Canvas for the Key Exploitable Result (KER) in the context of the PLOTO project outlines a comprehensive strategy for leveraging the project's outputs. This model highlights the crucial partnerships, activities, resources, and value propositions that are integral to the project's success. A strong emphasis is placed on collaboration with technical partners, end-users, and stakeholders across various sectors to ensure the solutions developed are both innovative and tailored to the specific needs of inland waterway transportation.

The value propositions are centered around offering advanced, integrated solutions that enhance the safety, efficiency, and sustainability of inland waterway operations. These solutions are designed to be adaptable, scalable, and capable of addressing the complex challenges faced by the industry. By focusing on customer relationships, the model aims to foster engagement with a broad spectrum of users through future research projects, licensing agreements, and continuous dissemination of findings.

The channels for exploitation include licensing agreements, academic publications, and cooperation with private companies and educational institutions. This multifaceted approach ensures that the innovations reach a wide audience and have a significant impact on the industry. The customer segments identified include service providers, civil protection agencies, research institutes, and entities involved in related EU-funded projects, highlighting the broad applicability and potential impact of the project's outcomes.

In terms of financial viability, the model outlines a clear cost structure, including research and development costs, collaboration expenses, and marketing efforts. The revenue streams are diversified, encompassing licensing agreements, consultancy services, and potential revenues from new EU-funded research projects. This financial strategy ensures the sustainability and growth of the project's exploitable results.

Through strategic partnerships, innovative solutions, and a focused approach to market engagement, the project is well-positioned to contribute significantly to the advancement and sustainability of inland waterway transportation in Europe.

8.3.2 BMC per KER

8.3.2.1 Fast assessment damage maps (satellite, ground sensor, and UAV-based).

Business model canvas for KER 2 Quick Damage Assessment Maps:

Key Partnerships:

- Collaboration with NTUA, STWS, UM.
- Collaboration with satellite and UAV service providers, sensor manufacturers, and data analysis firms.

Key Activities:

- Developing and integrating satellite, UAV-based, and ground sensor technologies to assess damage quickly.
- Collect input data. Create the water maps. Exploit the water maps.

Key Resources:

- Access to satellite images, UAVs, ground sensors, data processing technologies, and expert personnel in data analysis.

Value Propositions:

- Providing fast, accurate, and comprehensive damage assessments to aid rapid response and recovery efforts.
- The proposed workflow is a fully automated approach for river monitoring using Satellite data.

Customer Relationships:

- Establishing trust through reliable, timely, and actionable information, offering support and consultation for data interpretation.

Channels:

- Delivering maps and assessments through a dedicated platform, direct to customers (e.g., government agencies, emergency responders), and via APIs for integration into existing systems.

Customer Segments:

- Targeting emergency management agencies, government bodies, infrastructure companies, and insurance firms needing rapid damage assessment.
- As early adapters emphasis can be given to Organizations which manage IWW or the assets included.
- Research Centers

Cost Structure:

- Costs associated with satellite and UAV operations, sensor maintenance, data processing infrastructure, and skilled personnel.

Revenue Streams:

- Selling assessments as a service, subscription models for regular updates, and customized analysis services for specific incidents or regions.

8.3.2.2 Middleware and Data Fusion (DF) Services

Business model canvas for KER 7 Middleware and Data Fusion (DF) Services:

Key Partnerships:

- Collaboration among RISA, EXUS, INTRA, and other partners within the PLOTO project.
- Partnerships with providers of current information systems, sensor networks, and related technology platforms.

Key Activities:

- Development and integration of middleware to incorporate various information systems and sensor networks.
- Coordination of information delivery across network communication interfaces.

- Implementation of Data Fusion (DF) in a modular way across different layers to minimize complexity.
- Data definition; Integration mechanism definition; Middleware design and development.

Key Resources:

- Middleware technologies that enable effective and scalable service assurance and information delivery.
- Data Fusion technologies that integrate data from various sources for enhanced information accuracy and efficiency.
- End users' data, technical providers data, Sensors data.

Value Propositions:

- Providing an integrated platform that enhances data management and supports comprehensive analysis and decision-making.
- Offering a scalable solution that improves the resilience of IWW systems by effectively managing and fusing data from diverse sources.
- Middleware plays a crucial role in the overall architecture of an information technology (IT) system, serving as a bridge that connects different software applications and systems. It acts as an intermediary layer that facilitates communication, data exchange, and interoperability between disparate components within a complex IT environment.

Customer Relationships:

- Engaging with IWW organizations to upgrade their systems to meet EC standards and adapt to climate changes.
- Providing technical support and updates to ensure the middleware and DF services remain relevant and effective.
- Targeted Marketing Strategies.
- Prompt and helpful customer support through various channels.
- Effective Communication.

Channels:

- Direct sales to IWW operators, freight and passenger services, and other transport authorities.
- Marketing and dissemination through workshops, seminars, and online platforms.
- Own sales force
- Workshops and seminars
- System demonstration
- Marketing campaign (social media, paid search, email, videos, SEOs)
- Official website of PLOTO Project and RISA.

Customer Segments:

- IWW operators and other types of transport authorities.
- Users of IWW for freight and passenger services.
- Research organizations.
- Technical providers.

Cost Structure:

- Development costs for middleware and DF services.
- Costs associated with technical activities to increase the TRL (Technology Readiness Level) and system demonstrations.

Revenue Streams:

- Sales of middleware and DF services to IWW operators and transport authorities.

- Potential revenue from enhancing existing platforms for data management and entering new vertical business sectors.

8.3.2.3 Atmospheric Impact Assessment - Fore-Now/Casting Weather Predictions tool

Business model canvas for KER 9 Atmospheric Impact Assessment - Fore-Now/Casting Weather Predictions tool:

Key Partnerships:

- Collaboration between AUTH (Aristotle University of Thessaloniki) and FMI (Finnish Meteorological Institute) for development.
- Partnerships with other research institutions and commercial entities for further development and application.

Key Activities:

- Further development and application of the integrated nowcasting/forecasting modeling system.
- Provision of consulting services and training related to the system.

Key Resources:

- High-resolution modeling techniques for very local scale assessments.
- Operational mesoscale modeling techniques for covering extended areas.

Value Propositions:

- Providing detailed climatic and meteorological data in real-time at both local and meso scales.
- Enhancing the resilience of critical infrastructures against natural and man-made hazards, including potential climate change impacts.

Customer Relationships:

- Engaging with operators of critical infrastructures (e.g., IWW, road transport, ports, power generation, and water facilities) to offer tailored solutions.
- Providing ongoing support and updates to ensure the system's relevance and accuracy.

Channels:

- Direct sales and consulting services for the provision of the nowcasting/forecasting system.
- Dissemination through research activities, projects, and partnerships at national and international levels.

Customer Segments:

- Operators of critical infrastructures such as inland waterways, road transport, ports, power generation, and water facilities.
- Potential clients interested in acquiring the system for their purposes.

Cost Structure:

- Research and development costs for maintaining and enhancing the modeling system.
- Costs associated with providing consulting services and training.

Revenue Streams:

- Revenues from consulting services and training sessions offered to clients.
- Potential revenues from licensing the system or integrating it into commercial applications.

8.3.2.4 Integrated System - Integrated PLOTO platform

Business model canvas for KER 10 Integrated PLOTO platform:

Key Partnerships:

- Collaboration among all partners involved in the PLOTO project.

- Potential partnerships with organizations and entities interested in the platform's capabilities.

Key Activities:

- Further development and enhancement of the integrated PLOTTO platform.
- Offering consulting services and training to potential clients on the platform's use.

Key Resources:

- The integrated technology and software components of the PLOTTO platform.
- Expertise from consortium partners in deploying the platform.

Value Propositions:

- A comprehensive platform that integrates high technology with existing systems and facilities for improved service delivery.
- Capability to harmonize with other technologies and platforms, offering adaptable solutions for various infrastructural needs.

Customer Relationships:

- Engaging with IWW operators and maintenance teams through consulting services, training, and continuous support.
- Building long-term relationships by enhancing clients' service portfolios through the platform's deployment.

Channels:

- Direct engagement with potential clients through consortium networks.
- Marketing and dissemination of platform capabilities through workshops, seminars, and online platforms.

Customer Segments:

- IWW operators and maintenance and inspection teams of transport infrastructures.
- Entities interested in leveraging the platform for research activities or enhancing existing solutions.

Cost Structure:

- Development and enhancement costs of the platform.
- Costs related to marketing, training, and consulting services.

Revenue Streams:

- Revenue from consulting services and training offered to clients.
- Potential revenue from licensing the platform or components to interested parties.

8.3.2.5 Software for assessing risk by cointegrating exposure, hazard, and vulnerability - Risk Assessment Engine

Business model canvas for KER 11 Software for Assessing Risk by Cointegrating Exposure, Hazard, and Vulnerability - Risk Assessment Engine:

Key Partnerships:

- NTUA [Leader], SoReCC, end-users
- Collaboration with public and private entities for licensing and royalty-sharing agreements.
- Partnerships with research institutions for future research activities and projects.

Key Activities:

- Development of the risk assessment engine software.
- Exploitation of the software in future research projects.
- Assess the risk of the assets on a regional scale by integrating the source of hazard and the results of the multi-hazard vulnerability modules.

- Collaboration with entities for licensing and application of the software.

Key Resources:

- NTUA's expertise in risk assessment and software development.
- The risk assessment engine software.
- Multiple natural hazard scenarios / importance of the assets.

Value Propositions:

- Providing a comprehensive framework for assessing risks by integrating exposure, hazard, and vulnerability.
- Enhancing the safety and optimization of complex infrastructures through advanced risk modeling.
- Assess the impact of natural hazards on the assets of a region.
- Computationally frugal large-scale risk assessment for IWW.
- Assisting the rehabilitation/emergency action planning.

Customer Relationships:

- Engagement with customers through licensing agreements and consulting services.
- Dissemination of research findings and software applications through academic channels and partnerships.
- The KER will be deployed through NTUA communication and commercial channels.
Services to be provided:
 - Software-as-a-Service (SaaS), in which customers will purchase the Risk Assessment Engine on their own
 - Tool support & maintenance services.

Channels:

- Direct sales and licensing to city managers, service providers, and civil protection agencies.
- Distribution through academic publications, conferences, and other established channels.
- Co-operation with private companies and educational institutions, Own-channels

Customer Segments:

- City managers, service providers, civil protection agencies, research institutes, technological centers, universities, government bodies, and policy makers.
- Public authorities, catastrophe risk modelers, port operators, operations of infrastructure, academia.

Cost Structure:

- Development costs for the risk assessment engine.
- Costs associated with dissemination, licensing, and collaboration agreements.
- Start-up costs are calculated by estimating the number of Personnel Hours (PH) needed to develop and implement the component of the Business Plan (target TRL ≥ 8). No other costs are required.
- During development, testing and validation: $200 \text{ PH} * 42\text{€} = 8,400\text{€}$ Recurring expenses are calculated by estimating the number of Personnel Hours (PH) needed to develop and implement the component of the Business Plan. No other costs are required.
- After deployment:
 - Annual customer support expenses: $100 \text{ PH} * 32\text{€} = 3,200\text{€}$
 - Annual maintenance expenses: $100 \text{ PH} * 42\text{€} = 4,200\text{€}$
 - Marketing: 10% of the annual revenue for the 1st year - 5% of the annual revenue from the 3rd year and after.

Revenue Streams:

- Revenues from licensing agreements with public and private entities.
- Potential revenues from consulting services related to the application of the risk assessment engine.

- Revenues are calculated by estimating the Average Revenue Per User (ARPU) as follows:
- Initialisation cost: 8,000€ – 12,000€.
- The initialization cost depends on: (1) the number of Modules and Toolkits to be included, (2) the amount of data processed, and (3) the interaction requirements with the platform.
- Customization fee (optional): 50 PH * 150€ = 7,500€.
- The customization fee is related to the cost of integrating the Engine to the customer's legacy system, thus being optional.
- Annual royalty fee: 3,000€
- Expected number of customers:
- 1st year: 1 EU local port authority (either IWW or sea port), 1 EU Critical Infrastructure entity
- 2nd year: 2 EU local port authority, 1 US/global (either IWW or sea port), 2 EU Critical Infrastructure entity
- 3rd year: 4 EU local port authorities, 2 US/global (either IWW or sea port), 4 EU Critical Infrastructure entity.
- Other sources of revenues: Own budget, Angel investors, New EU-funded research projects

8.3.2.6 Socioeconomic impact assessment - Software for assessing socioeconomic impact

Business model canvas for KER 12 Socioeconomic Impact Assessment - Software for Assessing Socioeconomic Impact:

Key Partnerships:

- Collaboration with public and private entities such as governments, SMEs, and institutions to leverage the software's capabilities.
- Partnerships for further research and development activities to enhance the software's features.
- SoReCC [Leader], NTUA, end-users

Key Activities:

- Development and improvement of the socioeconomic impact assessment software.
- Providing advisory assignments and presenting the software's capabilities at international conferences.
- Collect input data, Use expert opinion.

Key Resources:

- SORECC's expertise in socioeconomic impact assessment and software development.
- Specialized datasets required for the software to conduct assessments.
- Input data: Economic data, Expert opinion, Exposure model of region under investigation, Business processes.

Value Propositions:

- Offering a comprehensive socioeconomic model that supports the resilience of IWW by assessing the impact on residents, the IWW-related economy, small businesses, and local governance.
- Flexibility to extend the software's application to other domains related to risk and resilience assessment, such as highways, urban areas, and cultural heritage.
- Assess the impact of natural hazards on a regional scale,
- Incorporation of multiple natural hazards
- Exploitation of available economic data, being downscaled or upscaled
- Focus, if necessary, on specific aspects, e.g., touristic area, area with cultural heritage, area close to sea or river
- Integration with business continuity models

Customer Relationships:

- Engaging with customers through advisory services, software customization, and training sessions to ensure the effective use of the software.
- Continuous support and updates to adapt the software to changing needs and requirements.
- The KER will be deployed through SoReCC's commercial channels.
- SoReCC will provide the following services:
 - Software-as-a-Service (SaaS), in which customers will purchase the Socioeconomic Engine on their own, using the online version of the tool
 - Tool support & maintenance services

Channels:

- Direct collaboration with targeted customers for the deployment of the software.
- Dissemination of software capabilities and services offered through academic and professional conferences, as well as through SORECC's network.
- Co-operation with private companies and educational institutions, Own channels

Customer Segments:

- City managers, service providers, civil protection agencies, research institutes, technological centers, universities, related EU-funded projects, government bodies, and policy makers.
- City managers, public authorities, port operators, academia.

Cost Structure:

- Development and maintenance costs of the socioeconomic impact assessment software.
- Costs associated with marketing, dissemination activities, and collaboration with partners.
- Start-up costs are calculated by estimating the number of Personnel Hours (PH) needed to develop and implement the component of the Business Plan (target TRL = 9).
- During development, testing and validation:
 - $500 \text{ PH} * 42\text{€} = 21,000\text{€}$
 - 3,000€ startup cost of the spin-off company.
- Recurring expenses are calculated by estimating the number of Personnel Hours (PH) needed to develop and implement the component of the Business Plan. No other costs are required.
- After deployment:
 - Annual cloud hosting resources: 1,000€
 - Annual customer support expenses: $50 \text{ PH} * 32\text{€} = 1,600\text{€}$
 - Annual maintenance expenses: $100 \text{ PH} * 42\text{€} = 4,200\text{€}$
 - Marketing: 12% of the annual revenue for the 1st year- 7% of the annual revenue from the 3rd year and after.

Revenue Streams:

- Revenue from advisory services provided to organizations using the software.
- Potential revenues from licensing the software to public and private entities.
- Revenues are calculated by estimating the Average Revenue Per User (ARPU) and the expected number of customers. ARPU is evaluated as follows:
 - Initialisation cost: 15,000€ – 20,000€
 - The initialisation cost depends: (1) on the amount of socioeconomic data to be integrated, and (2) on the level of analysis detail.
 - Customisation fee (optional): $50 \text{ PH} * 150\text{€} = 7,500\text{€}$
 - The customization fee is related to the cost of updating the socioeconomic data, thus being optional.
 - Annual subscription: 5,000€
 - The annual subscription is related to maintenance, support, and minor customizations

8.4 Project PLOT0 Lean canvas

The Lean Canvas is a business model framework that provides a concise and actionable way to capture the critical aspects of a business idea or an existing business. It is a modification of the Business Model Canvas (BMC) and was first proposed by Ash Maurya in his book "Scaling Lean" (Cai et al., 2019). The Lean Canvas comprises nine building blocks: customer segments, problems, unique value propositions, solutions, channels, cost structure, revenue streams, key metrics, and unfair advantage (Cai et al., 2019). It is designed to be a visual and iterative tool for startups to improve the effectiveness of startup exploration.

The Lean Canvas has been widely used in various contexts, including startups, entrepreneurship, and business development. It has been applied in the development and performance evaluation of academic spin-offs and in the context of software testing and agile startup methodologies. Additionally, the Lean Canvas has been utilized in designing user interfaces for startups and developing entrepreneurship data warehouses (Dahle et al., 2017).

The Lean Canvas for Project PLOT0, is structured as follows:

Problem: The problem lies in detailing the specific impacts of climate change on inland waterways (IWW), such as increased flooding or drought frequency, and explaining how these impacts affect infrastructure resilience.

Customer Segments: The customer segments include various infrastructure operators, such as those responsible for navigation, flood defenses, and water supply. Their unique needs and challenges must be highlighted to tailor solutions effectively.

Unique Value Proposition: The unique value proposition of PLOT0 is its introduction of technological advancements, such as AI-driven predictive models for water levels and infrastructure stress points. This offers a clear advantage over existing solutions.

Solution: The solution involves integrating real-time data analytics, advanced simulation tools, and dynamic response systems within the PLOT0 platform to address the identified problems effectively.

Channels: The communication strategies for engaging with stakeholders include enumerating workshops, webinars, and direct consultations to ensure widespread adoption and effective implementation of the solution.

Revenue Streams: Revenue streams can be outlined by considering potential pricing models for the platform's services, considering the value delivered in terms of reduced downtime and maintenance costs.

Cost Structure: The cost structure can be broken down to highlight investments in technology development, stakeholder engagement, and platform maintenance required to support the solution.

Key Metrics: Key performance indicators include reduced incident response times, accuracy of predictive analyses, and user satisfaction rates, which help measure the effectiveness of the solution.

Unfair Advantage: The unfair advantage is emphasized through exclusive access to specific datasets, proprietary algorithms, or partnerships with critical stakeholders that competitors cannot easily replicate.

8.5 Stakeholder engagement plan

Objective

To ensure successful engagement and exploitation of the PLOTO platform and its Key Exploitable Results (KERs) through effective communication and dissemination strategies targeting both internal networks of consortium partners and external stakeholders.

Engagement Through Partners' Networks:

- Leverage existing relationships and networks of consortium partners to engage stakeholders directly associated with or interested in the project outcomes.
- Utilize partners' communication channels, such as newsletters, direct emails, and social media platforms, to disseminate project information and invite stakeholders to participate in project-related events.

Engagement with External Stakeholders:

- Conduct a comprehensive stakeholder mapping exercise to identify and categorize external stakeholders by interest, influence, and potential impact on or benefit from the project.
- Organize industry-focused events, such as workshops and demonstration events, to showcase PLOTO outcomes, gather feedback, and foster collaboration.
- Establish a regular communication schedule using digital channels (website, social media, and newsletters) to keep stakeholders informed and engaged.
- Key Actions

Dissemination of Results:

- Develop clear and concise materials that articulate the purpose, aims, and benefits of the PLOTO platform for various stakeholder groups.
- Ensure regular updates on project progress, achievements, and upcoming events through established communication channels.

Stakeholder Mapping and Analysis:

- Identify key stakeholders within and outside the project scope, including industry experts, potential users, research institutions, policy makers, and community groups.
- Assess their potential impact on the project and interest in PLOTO outcomes to tailor engagement strategies effectively.

Organization of Events:

- Plan and execute a series of engagement activities, such as webinars, workshops, and demo days, to provide hands-on experience with PLOTO tools and solicit feedback.
- Utilize these events for network building and fostering partnerships for future exploitation of project results.

Digital Engagement:

- Enhance the project's digital presence through regular updates on the website, interactive social media campaigns, and engaging newsletters.
- Invite stakeholders to subscribe to the newsletter and follow PLOTO's social media channels for regular updates.

Monitoring and Evaluation

- Establish KPIs to measure the effectiveness of engagement activities, such as event attendance rates, newsletter subscription growth, social media engagement metrics, and stakeholder feedback.

- Regularly review and adjust the engagement plan based on stakeholder feedback and engagement metrics to ensure continuous improvement and alignment with project goals.

Timeline and Milestones

- Set specific milestones for each engagement activity, including preparation, execution, and follow-up stages, to ensure timely and coordinated efforts across the consortium.
- Schedule regular review meetings to assess progress against the engagement plan and adjust strategies as needed.

Responsibilities

- Assign clear roles and responsibilities to consortium partners for leading different aspects of the stakeholder engagement plan, ensuring a collaborative approach.
- Designate a dedicated team or individual for managing communications and organizing engagement events to maintain consistency and quality in stakeholder interactions.

9 Standardization and liaison plan

In this section, an overview of the information collected related to the standardisation landscape of the PLOTTO project is provided. Currently, very few specifications originating in traditional SDOs have been referenced in the deliverables. However, the project follows due to its nature a significant number of EU regulations and directives. Furthermore, map information, models and frameworks coming from openly available sources are largely included in the project's considerations. Such commonly available artefacts, accepted by a wide audience of stakeholders can be considered as “de-facto” standards even if not originating from a standardization organization.

As a starting point, a review of the submitted deliverables and the deliverables with the same submission date as the present document has been performed. Due to their nature, deliverables originating from WP1 (Project coordination and innovation management) and WP8 (Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Activities) do not deal with any standardization related topics and do hence not contribute to the PLOTTO standardization landscape.

WP2 (End-User Requirements and Platform Design) has as the main objective the production of the architectural specification of the PLOTTO integrated platform. The WP has already submitted all three deliverables. The template designed for the collection and description of the end-user requirements in D2.1 and refined in D2.2, is based on ISO/IEC/IEEE 29148:2018 “Systems and software engineering — Life cycle processes — Requirements engineering” which has been developed by ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 7/WG 7. The scope of the document is the specification of required processes implemented in engineering activities that result in requirements for systems and software products. However, this is focusing on the methodology used to achieve PLOTTO results but not related to these results in itself.

Of much higher significance are the European regulations and directives relevant to IWWs that have been taken into consideration in the specification of the End-User Requirements and the design of the PLOTTO platform.

- I. Regulations:
 - i. (EC) 718/1999 on a Community-fleet capacity policy to promote inland waterway transport
 - ii. (EU) 546/2014 amending Council Regulation (EC) No 718/1999 on a Community-fleet capacity policy to promote inland waterway transport
 - iii. (EC) 414/2007 concerning the technical guidelines for the planning, implementation and operational use of river information services (RIS) referred to in Article 5 of Directive 2005/44/EC (see below)
 - iv. (EU) 2018/97 on statistics of goods transport by inland waterways
 - v. (EC) 1365/2006 on statistics of goods transport by inland waterways
- II. Directives:
 - i. 2005/44/EC on harmonised river information services (RIS) on inland waterways in the Community
 - ii. 2000/60/EC establishing a framework for Community action in the field of water policy

Regulations and directives are not standards in themselves but as they are enforceable by law, they form a set of rules outlined by the government that must be followed as a minimum standard and

often contain references to standardization documents and mandate that the therein described requirements shall be fulfilled.

Deliverable D2.3 reports on the availability and specifications of geographical and other data services related to CC and geo-hazards. This includes 3D Digital Elevation Map data and map data provided through several sources such as the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (CLMS), the EU-Hydro River Network Database, and the European Environmental Agency’s (EEA) services. Such map data is not provided by a standardization organization but due to their common and free availability they can be considered de-facto standards in their field.

The observations made for D2.3 apply also for D3.1 where the bulk of the deliverable is based on climate data in the EURO-CORDEX archive. The other WP3 deliverable available at the time of writing the present document is D3.2 that reports on the dynamical downscaling of climate and atmospheric impacts. Again, no direct reference is made to standardization but the models described and used for the PLOTTO work (PALM LES model and the ICON weather-prediction model) and the EURO-CORDEX data provided by the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF) are widely used which may also make them de-facto standards.

WP4 (Vulnerability and Resilience Assessment of the IWW and the connected hinterland infrastructures) is currently working on two deliverables. However, at the time of writing the present document only incomplete versions of D4.1 and D4.3 were available. The review of these deliverables will therefore be covered in a later version of the PLOTTO standardization landscape.

9.1 Standardization bodies

DBC has proceeded to the necessary actions to identify whether there any affiliations of project partners with standardization bodies. The “PLOTTO - T8.6 Standardisation working groups” xcl document was created and provided to the partners in order for them to provide DBC with any relative information.

Following the feedback received, several PLOTTO partners were identified to be active in various standardization organizations. In this subsection, a list of the organizations and the partner activities are presented, with reference to the relevance of the standard to the PLOTTO framework and the contact person of each partner (Table 12).

Table 12: Partner - standardisation body correspondence

Partner	Standardization body	Relevance of standard to PLOTTO	Partner’s contact person in standardization body
NTUA	CEN/TC250	Structural Eurocodes are relevant to all hinterland assets of civil engineering significance, such as piers and buildings	Philippe Bisch
NTUA	EAAE/WG13	WG13 is the main instrument for influencing advancements in seismic codes on industrial facilities, comprising the backbone of many commercial ports	Fabrizio Paolacci

FMI	CEN/TC 264/WG12	Assessing ambient air quality is strongly related especially to PLOTO: "IMP4 - Reduce environmental impact" and to project Objectives: STO-1, STO-2, STO-3, STO-4, STO-5, STO-6;	Heidi Hellén
FMI	CEN/TC 264/WG13	Assessing ambient air quality is strongly related especially to PLOTO: "IMP4 - Reduce environmental impact" and to project Objectives: STO-1, STO-2, STO-3, STO-4, STO-5, STO-6;	Heidi Hellén
FMI	CEN/TC 264/WG15	Assessing ambient air quality is strongly related especially to PLOTO: "IMP4 - Reduce environmental impact" and to project Objectives: STO-1, STO-2, STO-3, STO-4, STO-5, STO-6;	Karri Saarnio
FMI	CEN/TC 264/WG35	Assessing ambient air quality is strongly related especially to PLOTO: "IMP4 - Reduce environmental impact" and to project Objectives: STO-1, STO-2, STO-3, STO-4, STO-5, STO-6;	Karri Saarnio
FMI	CEN/TC 264/WG42	Assessing ambient air quality is strongly related especially to PLOTO: "IMP4 - Reduce environmental impact" and to project Objectives: STO-1, STO-2, STO-3, STO-4, STO-5, STO-6;	Karri Saarnio
FMI	CEN/TC 264/WG43	Modelling ambient air quality is strongly related especially to PLOTO: "IMP4 - Reduce environmental impact" and to project Objectives: STO-1, STO-2, STO-3, STO-4, STO-5, STO-6;	Ari Karppinen
FMI	CEN/TC 264/WG44	Assessing ambient air quality and the source contribution of waterways traffic is strongly related especially to PLOTO: "IMP4 - Reduce environmental impact" and to project Objectives: STO-1, STO-2, STO-3, STO-4, STO-5, STO-6;	Ari Karppinen

The necessary actions will be undertaken in order for the aforementioned connections to be exploited for the purpose of development of the PLOTO results according to the applicable standards and the national security/safety-related regulation and/or directives. DBC will continue their task of identifying any additional affiliations of partners to any standardization bodies, thus ensuring that the standardization activities will be carried out properly. DBC, the partner in charge of conduction of the standardization plan and organization of the related activities, will ensure that throughout the course of the PLOTO project, the partners will be in continuous contact with and participate in standardization working groups (SWGs) related to the fields of sensors, communication and monitoring.

9.2 Other cooperation and liaising activities

As already mentioned in the previous edition of this deliverable, an essential activity of the PLOTO project is to create links and natural synergies with other EU-funded initiatives. The preliminary list of projects identified in Table 13 is the result of partners' efforts and presents a series of initiatives funded under the same call (HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01-09) and with projects funded under other calls but with relevance to PLOTO scope.

In the first 18 months of projects, the Consortium has actively engaged in building external relations with some of the below-mentioned projects. With sister projects CRISTAL and ReNEW there has been

an active collaboration to participate to events namely the Inland Waterway Week organised in May 2023 and the Transport Research Arena Conference planned in April 2024. Furthermore, FOR-FREIGHT project has been invited to participate in the Plenary Meeting held in Athens on 7-8 February 2024. This allowed partners to understand the potential connections between the two projects and collaborate on joint participations to upcoming events.

In June 2023, the PLOTO project also signed the [partnership agreement](#) with the European Technology Platform (ETP) ALICE to join their liaison programme, which will support the dissemination, cross-fertilisation and outreach of PLOTO, as well as help to promote the exploitation of PLOTO's technological innovations and support their market uptake.

In the upcoming months, the effort will be to strengthen these collaborations with soon-to-be-planned activities, such as drafting a joint white paper and co-organising a workshop, already included in the Dissemination KPIs' table (Table 5).

Table 13: Table 6. List of projects-initiatives related to PLOTO

Project Title	Link	Relevance to PLOTO	Participating partner from PLOTO (if any)	Responsible partner(s) from PLOTO	Funded under HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01-09	Actively engaged with
CRISTAL	http://www.cristal-project.eu/	Funded under same call.	No	DBC	Yes	Yes
ReNEW	https://www.inlandwaterwaytransport.eu/renew-project/	Funded under same call.	No	DBC	Yes	Yes
For-Freight	https://www.for-freight.eu/	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01-07	No	DBC	No	Yes
HYPERION	https://www.hyperion-project.eu/	Employs similar technologies, but for cultural heritage and urban area risk	NTUA, RISA	NTUA	No	
THETIDA	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101095253	Employs similar technologies, but for underwater cultural heritage risk	NTUA	NTUA	No	
Green Win	https://www.nweurope.eu/projects/project-search/greenwin-greener-waterway-infrastructure/	Focused on improving management of IWW (although from the perspective of energy efficiency); but it will end in 2023	ULIEGE		No	

10 Conclusions

This deliverable presents the updated versions of the dissemination, communication, exploitation and IPR management plans of the PLOTTO project. The plans have been proactive, including:

- (a) Communication and Dissemination plan: Variations in the current digital trends are affecting the use of some of the social media platforms listed above so the Key Performance Indicators should be revised.
- (b) Exploitation and IPR management: A further analysis of the Inland waterway transport (IWT) market in Europe and the respective competition. Elaboration of the IPR Management and standardisation plan presented in D8.2.

The PLOTTO team will use this document to establish a common understanding of the procedures that will be followed during the project's lifetime to maintain a high-quality and constant communication channel with the public. The document is also considered as a living report, as through the precise monitoring and control of the PLOTTO activities, plan adaptations and updates are expected, following related dissemination and communication opportunities, as well as plan alignment with the project's technical outcomes and major dissemination activities (workshops' organisation, participation in large events, organisation of training activities, etc.).

Furthermore, in month 42, the plan, informed by the outcomes of the third exploitation workshop will be finalised. That version will incorporate a strategy for defining measures for exploitation in the "after the project" phase, demonstrating best practices in capturing and assessing IP agreements concerning ownership, rights of use, and agreements on the maintenance of the PLOTTO software and its components. Additionally, roll-out plans for end-users and establish a roadmap for deployment to external end-users will be developed. Finally, we will analyze key parameters from socio-economic aspects, such as job creation and effects on GDP and import/export, based on the entire value chains.

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Annex A: KPIs table

KPI No	KPI Name	KPI Description
KPI1	Reliable quantification of climatic, hydrological and atmospheric stressors.	Identification and specialization of 20 climate indicators in connection with specific Impacts per use case. Downscaling and high-resolution mapping of climate impacts based on (minimum) two long-term climatic scenarios (baseline & worst case).: Yes or No (boolean)
KPI2	Development of a forecasting module.	Improved skill scores (e.g., Critical Success Index (CSI) for deterministic and Brier score for probabilistic) of the hot-spot precipitation forecasts over different lead-times. : Yes or No (boolean)
KPI3	Development of advanced Remote-Sensing (RS) algorithms, multi-hazard modelling and AI tools for accurate IWW mapping and multi-hazard maps.	Novel learning methods for probabilistically detecting flaws in infrastructure in n-RT (just-in-time) processing complexity. We target to minimise both false positive and negative rates (target >25%, based on estimations from relevant projects, such as PANOPTIS, ZONESEC and RESIST). Novel learning methods for mapping land cover changes and detecting floods/landslides. Improved DInSAR methodologies.: Yes or No (boolean)
KPI4	ML models prediction performance	Mean Absolute Percentage Error: ≤20% on all defined locations
KPI5	Design of a COP including an enhanced visualisation interface and an IMS.	Quantifying risk of disasters & Pre-disaster situation: Hazard exposure, vulnerability, resilience, risk status, evacuation plans and modelling scenarios. Deliver data, info, products significantly sooner (30%) than COPERNICUS EMS.: Yes or No (boolean)
KPI6	Improved efficiency of data.	Improved efficiency of marine traffic handling, decreased wait times, fewer disruption days due to natural hazards.: Yes or No (boolean)

KPI7	Establish long-term data platforms securing open, consistent data points.	Fuse all generated and collected data on both the PLOTTO platform and in a common open repository (OpenAIRE, Zenodo, GitHub), achieving 100% availability for non-proprietary data, and at least 80% for proprietary (anonymized, non-confidential) data, while promoting a unified format for (IWW and non-IWW) infrastructure data representation and archiving.: Yes or No (boolean)
KPI8	Sensors / Services	Capability of the system for flexible and efficient integration of multiple services and sensors.: Number of integrated services and sensors ≥ 10
KPI9	Sensors	Capability of the system to be able to accept, store and provide information from all PLOTTO sensors.: Connected sensors displayed in IWAT/COP
KPI10	Data Processors	Capability of the system to handle multiple sources of data.: Number of Data Processors (≥ 10)
KPI11	Historical Data	The system should store data and metadata and allow historical look up and display (through the COP/IWAT).: Yes or No (boolean)
KPI12	Data updates on restoring communications	Capability of the system to restore the "lost" data upon communication recovery.: Yes or No (boolean)
KPI13	Data fusion	The system shall develop algorithms that combine information to improve accuracy.: Yes or No (boolean)
KPI14	Data fusion	The data fusion service should be able to combine alerts and provide a more concrete alarm (>1 alerts combined) to the operator.: Yes or No (boolean)
KPI15	Data fusion	Capability of the system to identify when a certain number of alerts illustrate incompatibility between location and/or time and generate a relevant alarm.: Yes or No (boolean)
KPI16	Data fusion	Capability of the data fusion service to merge multiple alarms that refer to the same event: Yes or No (boolean)
KPI17	Data fusion	The data fusion service will produce additional alarms for events that will be based on data concerning certain areas of interest.: Yes or No (boolean)
KPI18	Sensors / Services	Capability of the system to generate an alert when a sensor and/or service is no longer available: Yes or No (boolean)

KPI19	Water coverage/level	Capability of the system to compile data representation for water coverage/level assessment.: Yes or No (boolean)
KPI20	Water coverage/level	Capability of the system to calculate water coverage changes.: Yes or No (boolean)
KPI21	Water coverage/level	Capability of the system to calculate water level changes.: Yes or No (boolean)
KPI22	Water coverage/level	Capability of the system to assess flooding/drought conditions.: Yes or No (boolean)
KPI23	COP	Information from more than 3 data sources should be presented to the COP simultaneously. Number of data sources: >3
KPI24	COP	Number of assets depicted on COP map (without clustering) without flickering ~ 1000 objects Number of objects on the map > 1000
KPI25	COP	COP refresh updates -> Less than 5 seconds (assumes sufficient communication bandwidth in the field and the updated information is available to the middleware) COP refresh rate: <5 seconds
KPI26	IMS	IMS could support response plans with more than 50 actions steps Number of action steps per plan: > 50
KPI27	IMS	IMS could support the management of more than one incident simultaneously. Number of incidents: >1
KPI28	IWAT	IWAT could support more than 50 users connected simultaneously. Number of connected users: >50

Annex B: PESTLE Analyses for ERs

ER1: Enhanced Computer vision for damage diagnosis and Machine Learning (ML) techniques.

Political: EU policies on transport infrastructure and innovation funding could support the adoption of these technologies. International cooperation may influence standards in computer vision and ML applications.

Economic: Investment in smart infrastructure and the competitive landscape of technology providers could affect the economic viability and adoption rates of such innovations.

Social: Public acceptance and workforce skills in advanced technologies could impact the deployment and effectiveness of these systems.

Technological: Advances in computer vision, ML, and sensor technologies will directly influence the capabilities and performance of damage diagnosis systems.

Legal: Regulations on data privacy, drone usage, and AI governance could pose challenges or provide frameworks for deploying these technologies.

Environmental: The application of these technologies in monitoring and mitigating environmental impacts through improved infrastructure resilience could align with sustainability goals.

ER3: Seamless integration of data from multiple sensors on UAVs, fixed ground stations, and moving vehicles for damage mapping and monitoring.

Political: The technology could be influenced by governmental policies on drone usage, data sharing between countries, and international collaborations in disaster response and environmental monitoring.

Economic: The development and deployment costs, as well as the potential for cost savings in disaster management and infrastructure maintenance, are economic considerations. Market demand for integrated monitoring solutions could also influence economic viability.

Social: Public perception of drone usage and privacy concerns, along with the social impact of improved disaster response and environmental monitoring, would be relevant factors.

Technological: Advances in sensor technology, data integration methods, and the development of standards for multi-sensor data fusion are key technological considerations. The pace of technological change could also affect the long-term viability of the solution.

Legal: Data privacy laws, airspace regulations for drones, and international standards for data sharing and environmental monitoring are important legal factors.

Environmental: The technology's role in monitoring environmental changes, its impact on wildlife, and its contribution to sustainable disaster response and infrastructure maintenance are environmental considerations.

ER4: IWW Simulators with climate scenarios and new data emanating from the project outcomes.

Political: Policies on climate change and environmental protection, as well as international cooperation on waterway management and disaster preparedness, could influence the development and use of these simulators.

Economic: The financial support for climate adaptation technologies and the potential cost savings from using simulators for infrastructure planning and disaster mitigation could play a significant role.

Social: Public awareness and concern about climate change impacts, as well as the demand for innovative solutions to protect communities and infrastructure, could drive interest and acceptance of simulation technologies.

Technological: Advances in simulation software, climate modelling, and data analytics, as well as integration capabilities with existing systems, are crucial for the development and effectiveness of these simulators.

Legal: Regulations related to waterway management, climate adaptation measures, and the use of simulation in planning and decision-making processes could impact the deployment of IWW simulators.

Environmental: The application of these simulators to model climate scenarios and their effects on inland waterways would directly contribute to understanding and mitigating environmental challenges, aligning with sustainability goals.

ER5: Multi-Hazard Vulnerability Modules and Assessment Toolkit for IWW

Political: The adoption and integration of the toolkit may be influenced by national and EU-level policies on infrastructure resilience, climate adaptation strategies, and disaster risk management, emphasizing the need for such tools in planning and policy-making.

Economic: The economic implications of improved risk assessment and disaster management could lead to cost savings in infrastructure maintenance, emergency response, and recovery efforts. Funding for research and development in this area, as well as potential economic benefits from licensing agreements, are also relevant.

Social: The toolkit's potential to enhance public safety and reduce vulnerability to natural hazards can have significant social implications. Public acceptance of new technologies for disaster preparedness and the role of community engagement in vulnerability assessments are also considered.

Technological: Advances in modelling techniques, data analytics, and software development are critical for the toolkit's development and effectiveness. Integration with existing systems and interoperability with other tools and platforms are also key technological considerations.

Legal: Compliance with data protection regulations, especially when handling sensitive information related to vulnerabilities and risks, is a legal factor. Intellectual property rights and licensing agreements for the software and data formats developed are also important.

Environmental: The toolkit directly addresses environmental challenges by incorporating climate change scenarios and environmental model inputs. It supports sustainable infrastructure planning and disaster risk reduction efforts in the face of changing environmental conditions.

ER6: COP and IMS, adapted to PLOT needs and selected scenarios

Political: The deployment of COP and IWAT solutions could be influenced by governmental policies related to smart cities, mobility solutions, and public safety. Regulations and standards for infrastructure management and data sharing across jurisdictions can also impact the adoption of these technologies.

Economic: The development and commercialization of these solutions could be affected by the level of investment in smart infrastructure and digital transformation projects by public and private entities. Economic factors also include the potential for these solutions to create cost savings and efficiency gains in infrastructure management.

Social: Public acceptance of smart infrastructure solutions and concerns about privacy and data protection can influence the social feasibility of deploying COP and IWAT technologies. The potential for these technologies to enhance public safety and quality of life could drive social demand.

Technological: Advances in software for infrastructure analysis, risk mitigation, and maintenance support are crucial. The integration capabilities of these technologies with existing infrastructure and systems, as well as their adaptability to evolving smart city technologies, are key technological considerations.

Legal: Compliance with data protection laws, intellectual property rights, and regulations governing infrastructure management and public safety are important legal factors. The absence of conflicting IP within the project is beneficial, but navigating the IP landscape in the broader market is necessary.

Environmental: While not directly mentioned, the environmental impact of these technologies can be considered in terms of their contribution to sustainable infrastructure management and resilience to environmental changes, particularly in the context of smart cities and mobility solutions.

ER8: Coupled Multi-nested Local Scale Modelling

Political: Climate modelling and urban heat island mitigation strategies are increasingly supported by government policies aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions and adapting to climate change. Political backing can facilitate funding and implementation of such models in urban planning. The complexity of climate models and their relevance across borders encourage international cooperation in research and data sharing, influenced by global climate agreements and initiatives.

Economic: Economic factors include the allocation of funding for research and development in climate science and urban planning. Investment in these areas can drive innovation and the adoption of new technologies. Effective climate modelling can lead to more efficient urban planning, reducing costs associated with climate change adaptation and mitigation. It can also influence real estate values and development costs.

Sociological: The societal impact is significant as increased awareness and education about climate change can lead to greater public support for sustainable urban planning and lifestyle changes. Involving local communities in the planning process can lead to more effective and socially acceptable solutions for mitigating urban heat islands and adapting to climate impacts.

Technological: The development of coupled multi-nested local scale modelling benefits from advancements in computational technologies and data analytics, allowing for more accurate and detailed simulations. The ability to integrate these models with existing urban planning tools and technologies can enhance the effectiveness of urban designs in mitigating climate impacts.

Legal: Legal factors include the development of regulations and standards related to urban planning and construction, aimed at reducing heat island effects and improving resilience to climate change. Ensuring that new developments comply with these standards requires robust enforcement mechanisms and potentially new legal frameworks.

Environmental: The primary environmental consideration is the model's role in adapting to and mitigating the effects of climate change, particularly in urban areas where heat islands exacerbate local temperatures. Urban planning informed by these models can also consider the impact on local biodiversity and the provision of ecosystem services, promoting green infrastructure and sustainable land use.

ER13: River Digital Twin

Political: The deployment of the IWW Digital Twin could be influenced by regulatory frameworks and policies promoting digital innovation and sustainability in the transport sector. Compliance with international standards for digital twin technology in infrastructure management could also play a crucial role.

Economic: The economic viability of the IWW Digital Twin hinges on the demand for advanced digital solutions in infrastructure management, the investment required for system implementation and maintenance, and the potential cost savings from improved efficiency, predictive maintenance, and risk management.

Social: The acceptance and use of digital twin technology by infrastructure operators and the wider community, especially in terms of safety and efficiency improvements, could impact the social feasibility of deploying the IWW Digital Twin. Data privacy concerns related to personal data collection might also influence social acceptance.

Technological: The integration of machine learning to learn from real-time data and the ability to simulate various scenarios for better decision-making represent technological strengths. However, the need for significant investment in time and resources for system implementation and the challenge of ensuring data quality could pose technological limitations.

Legal: The absence of conflicting IPs at the project stage is beneficial, but navigating the complex landscape of intellectual property rights, data protection, and privacy laws will be crucial as the technology is further developed and commercialized.

Environmental: The IWW Digital Twin's capabilities in environmental monitoring and predicting the impact of environmental factors on infrastructure can contribute to more sustainable infrastructure management and resilience against natural disasters.

Annex C: SWOT Analyses for ERs

ER1: Enhanced Computer Vision for damage diagnosis and ML techniques.

Strengths:

- Integration of multi-sensor data and advanced computer vision algorithms.
- Ability to assess damage and degradation for various disaster scenarios, ensuring efficient maintenance and early detection of hazards.
- Rapid post-hazard damage inspection and performance assessment capabilities.

Weaknesses:

- Competitiveness depends on the final product's level, with data availability and quality potentially impacting results.

Opportunities:

- Potential applicability in other fields, such as cultural heritage monitoring or mobile mapping.
- Interest from inspection and maintenance industries in the developed system.

Threats:

- Potential skepticism from stakeholders and end-users unfamiliar with the technology.

ER3: Seamless integration of data from multiple sensors on UAVs, fixed ground stations, and moving vehicles for damage mapping and monitoring

Strengths:

- Experience in providing satellite and UAV-based location assessments and strong existing know-how in the subject.

Weaknesses:

- IWW is a new market domain for STWS, and regulations on drone flights could significantly hinder rapid, on-demand assessments.

Opportunities:

- The growing and underutilized inland waterway transport market offers room for novel solutions, supported by a well-composed consortium to mature the technology.

Threats:

- High potential for the solution to be copied by competitors.
- Rapid technological advancements in drone-based products could quickly make existing solutions obsolete.
- Reliance on strong IP protection to maintain competitive advantage.

ER4: IWW Simulators with climate scenarios and new data emanating from the project outcomes

Strengths:

- Holistic risk and resilience assessment capabilities.
- Unified assessment of impacts between interconnected IWW sites/elements for various perils.

- A unique integrated platform for operational picture and incident management.

Weaknesses:

- The software requires specialized analyses for input data, making it generally applicable but needing significant customization for each client or case study.
- Reluctance from end-users to provide detailed asset risk information.
- Simplifications are necessary for large-scale applications like IWW and urban areas.

Opportunities:

- Potential application across various infrastructure types, attracting diverse stakeholders like highway operators, urban planners, and cultural heritage owners.
- Emerging markets present new opportunities for application and growth.

Threats:

- Established competition from large companies and universities in the EU, US, and Asia.
- Competitive technologies and products in catastrophe modeling pose a challenge.

ER5: Multi-Hazard Vulnerability Modules and Assessment Toolkit for IWW

Strengths:

- Representation of a wide range of assets at risk, considering IWW elements and interconnected non-IWW components affecting infrastructure performance.
- Detailed models for critical assets and reliable surrogate models for others.
- Correlation with measured data for near-real-time vulnerability assessment of IWW infrastructure.
- Incorporation of environmental model inputs, field data, material parameter uncertainties, and climate change effects using diverse sources.
- Development of fully probabilistic, age-dependent models for infrastructure, incorporating epistemic uncertainties.

Weaknesses:

- Lack of detailed data for critical assets.
- Requirement for a hydrological model for IWW.
- Some data sources are protected and may need customization or anonymization for efficient use.

Opportunities:

- Applicability to other fields, such as the impact of climate change on critical infrastructure.
- Potential in emerging markets.

Threats:

- Competition from large private companies and universities in the US and Asia.
- Other competitive technologies, products, or solutions in the field of catastrophe modeling.

ER6: COP and IWAT were adapted to PLOTTO needs and selected scenarios.

Strengths:

- Provides end-to-end and enterprise-level solutions for managing large and critical infrastructures.
- The PLOTO consortium's ideal composition of partners facilitates the piloting and market deployment of the proposed solution.
- Unique in the market with no equivalent direct competition.

Weaknesses:

- New entrants like STWS may face challenges due to strong brand loyalty towards established firms, making it difficult to gain market share.
- Competitive firms might hold patents restricting new entrants from competing in specific areas, and the fixed costs for research and development in these markets are steep.

Opportunities:

- The new technologies developed in the PLOTO project could disrupt established competition, allowing STWS to enter the market.
- While established market players cover existing needs, the COP&IWAT solution caters to an unmet market need, offering new opportunities.

Threats:

- Regulatory barriers local governments create could pose significant risks for STWS entering the IWW market in different countries, limiting expansion potential.
- The IWW market might have existing monopolies that are difficult to penetrate. Key players in the Waterway Transportation Software and Services Market could create competitive forces against STWS and the PLOTO consortium.

ER8: Coupled Multi-nested Local Scale Modelling

Strengths:

- **Advanced Modelling Techniques:** Utilizes state-of-the-art modelling approaches, enhancing the accuracy and reliability of weather and climate predictions.
- **Multi-Nested Approach:** Allows for a more detailed and localized analysis, improving the model's performance in specific regions, which is crucial for targeted applications like urban planning, agriculture, and disaster management.
- **Integration Capabilities:** Designed to be coupled with other models and data sources, increasing its versatility and applicability across various domains.
- **Support for Decision Making:** The improved precision and reliability of the model can significantly aid in decision-making processes for policymakers, businesses, and communities, particularly in planning for and mitigating the impacts of climate change and extreme weather events.

Weaknesses:

- **Complexity:** The advanced nature and multi-nested approach of the model could lead to increased complexity, making it challenging to understand, use, and maintain, especially for users without technical expertise.

- **Resource Intensity:** High computational demands could limit accessibility for institutions with limited resources and could increase operational costs.
- **Data Requirements:** The effectiveness of the model is heavily dependent on the availability and quality of input data, which could be a limiting factor in regions with poor data collection infrastructure.

Opportunities:

- **Technological Advancements:** Continuous improvements in computational power and data collection (e.g., satellite technology, IoT) could enhance the model's performance and reduce operational costs.
- **Collaborations and Partnerships:** Potential for collaboration with academic institutions, government agencies, and private sector players in climate science, urban planning, agriculture, and disaster management, expanding its applicability and impact.
- **Climate Change Awareness:** Growing awareness and concern over climate change could drive demand for advanced modelling solutions, positioning the exploitable result at the forefront of this field.
- **Policy and Regulation:** Increasingly stringent environmental and urban planning regulations may necessitate more accurate and localized climate models, creating a market for such advanced modelling solutions.

Threats:

- **Competition:** The rapid pace of technological advancement in the field of climate modelling could lead to the emergence of more advanced or user-friendly alternatives.
- **Funding and Economic Constraints:** Economic downturns or shifts in funding priorities could impact the development and implementation of such advanced models.
- **Technological Obsolescence:** The rapid evolution of technology in modelling and data processing could render current methodologies obsolete, requiring continuous updates and improvements.
- **Data Privacy and Security:** The model's reliance on vast amounts of data could raise concerns regarding data privacy and security, particularly if sensitive or personal data are involved.

ER13: IWW Digital Twin

Strengths:

- Offers an improved understanding of the port's processes and systems, leading to more efficient and effective operations.
- Predicts potential flooding or drought, preventing asset damage, reducing downtime, and improving safety.
- Utilizes Machine Learning (ML) to learn from real-time data for better predictions and decision-making.
- Allows testing of different scenarios and outcomes for informed decision-making.
- Enhances communication and collaboration among stakeholders with digital twin technology.
- Increases efficiency and reduces downtime, resulting in cost savings.

- Predicts flooding or drought, aiding in preparation and prevention of asset damage.

Weaknesses:

- Implementation and maintenance might be costly, requiring significant time and resources.
- Data availability and quality could impact the system's predictions' accuracy and usefulness.
- May not account for all potential scenarios or factors affecting the port's operations.

Opportunities:

- Capabilities expansion to include other aspects of port operations like security or cargo tracking.
- Integration with other digital systems for a comprehensive operational view and risk assessment.
- Identifying operational improvement areas, leading to increased efficiency and profitability.

Threats:

- Resistance from stakeholders unfamiliar with digital twin technology and its benefits.
- Data privacy concerns if the personal data of workers or visitors are collected and used.
- Cybersecurity risks threaten the system's accuracy and reliability.
- Competition from traditional risk management methods and conventional simulation software, which might be less comprehensive or flexible than a digital twin system. Digital twin technology is relatively new in port operations and risk management, so the competitive landscape may evolve with technology adoption and innovations.

Annex D: BMC Analyses for ERs

ER1: Enhanced Computer vision for damage diagnosis and Machine Learning (ML) techniques.

Business model canvas for KER.1 Computer Vision Detection System, focusing on enhanced computer vision for damage diagnosis and Machine Learning (ML) techniques:

Key Partnerships:

- Collaborations with academic institutions for research and development.
- Partnerships with technology providers and data analytics companies.

Key Activities:

- Development of enhanced computer vision methods and ML techniques for damage diagnosis.
- Integration of these technologies into a comprehensive monitoring and mapping system for IWW corridors.

Key Resources:

- Advanced computer vision and ML algorithms.
- Expertise in data analysis and environmental issue assessment.

Value Propositions:

- It provides a system integrating multi-sensor data and advanced computer vision algorithms for accurate damage diagnosis.
- It enables early detection of damage, degradation, and emerging hazards for efficient maintenance and rapid post-hazard damage inspection.

Customer Relationships:

- It is establishing long-term relationships with ministries, municipalities, and organizations managing IWW and transport infrastructures through continuous support and updates.

Channels:

- Direct sales to ministries, municipalities, transport operators, and infrastructure maintenance teams.
- Distribute the system or its internal algorithms to upcoming projects on a contract basis.

Customer Segments:

- Ministries, municipalities, and organizations are involved in managing or exploiting IWW and transport infrastructures.
- Maintenance and inspection teams of transport infrastructures.

Cost Structure:

- Research and development costs for enhancing computer vision and ML technologies.
- Costs associated with data acquisition and processing.

Revenue Streams:

- Licensing of the overall system or its internal advanced algorithms to various municipalities, countries, and organizations.
- Service delivery contracts for specific projects requiring the system's capabilities.

ER3: Seamless integration of data from multiple sensors on UAVs, fixed ground stations, and moving vehicles for damage mapping and monitoring.

Business model canvas for KER 3 UAV Inspection, focusing on the seamless integration of data from multiple sensors on UAVs, fixed ground stations, and moving vehicles for damage mapping and monitoring:

Key Partnerships:

- STWS [Leader], end-users

- Collaboration with drone technology companies, satellite imagery providers, and data analytics firms.
- Potential partnerships with companies listed as competitors for joint ventures or technology sharing.

Key Activities:

- Integration and analysis of data collected from UAVs, fixed ground stations, and moving vehicles.
- Continuous development and enhancement of UAV technology and data integration platforms.
- Involve developing algorithms and interfaces for real-time data processing and analysis, which is crucial for accurate and comprehensive damage assessment and monitoring.

Key Resources:

- Advanced UAV technology, satellite imagery, fixed ground station data, and integrated software platforms.
- Drone data, open geospatial and field data
- Expertise in data analysis, UAV operation, and disaster mitigation strategies.

Value Propositions:

- Providing comprehensive and real-time on-site damage assessments to facilitate rapid response and mitigation strategies.
- Offering enhanced risk engineering, safer and more cost-effective site inspections, and high-quality visual assessments for risk management.
- Ability to provide a comprehensive and real-time overview of river conditions by integrating data from various sources. This aids in accurate damage assessment, proactive infrastructure maintenance, and effective environmental monitoring, crucial for inland waterway operators, public safety organizations, and regional authorities. The system's versatility and depth of data offer a significant advantage in managing and protecting river ecosystems and infrastructure.

Customer Relationships:

- Establishing long-term partnerships with critical infrastructure operators and insurance companies.
- Providing ongoing support, training, and updates to enhance customer engagement and satisfaction.
- Designing and implementing specific solutions that align with client requirements and specifications.

Channels:

- Direct sales to inland waterways infrastructure operators, critical infrastructure owners, first/disaster responders, and insurance companies.
- Marketing through industry conferences, digital platforms, and direct engagement with potential clients.
- The concept and system components are presented to public safety organizations, such as the Greek fire service, the General Secretariat of Civil Protection, and authorities with whom Satways has professional relations and contacts.

Customer Segments:

- Inland Waterways infrastructure operators, critical infrastructure owners, first/disaster response organizations, and insurance companies.
- Also, the system targets a combined customer base that includes inland waterway operators, public safety organizations, and local and regional river authorities. It provides a comprehensive solution for real-time monitoring and assessment of river conditions and infrastructure, aiding in informed decision-making for emergency responses, maintenance, and environmental protection along inland waterways.

Cost Structure:

- Investment in UAV technology, research and development for data integration solutions, and IP protection.
- Costs associated with marketing, sales, and customer support.
- The one-time start-up costs of the business are estimated to be between €430,000 and €700,000, which includes software development, assets/sensors procurement, system testing, and other long-term assets. The recurring expenses are estimated to be between €45,000 and €70,000 per year, which includes maintenance and professional fees, data storage and cloud services, marketing costs, and office and plant overhead. The expected revenues are based on the service's pricing model, sales forecasts, and financing preferences. The starting capital can be acquired through investors or loans. The pricing strategy is based on competitive market analysis. The sales forecast is estimated based on market demand and outreach. The financing preferences will determine the balance between debt and equity financing.

Revenue Streams:

- Selling services for damage mapping and monitoring to targeted customer segments.
- Licensing of technology and data to other companies and organizations.
- Customized solutions and consulting services for risk assessment and disaster mitigation.
- The following revenue streams could be considered. This approach should be revised toward the end of the project. The primary source is Service -Based Revenue, where clients pay for access to data and analysis tools, potentially through subscriptions or on e-time project fees. Adding to this are Customization and Consulting Fees, charged for tailoring the system to client-specific requirements and providing expert data analysis. Collaborative ventures can open Partnerships and Data Sharing opportunities with government and research entities. Lastly, Training and Support Services offer additional revenue from educating clients on system usage and offering technical support.

ER4: IWW Simulators with climate scenarios and new data emanating from the project outcomes.

Business model canvas for the KER 4 IWW Simulators with climate scenarios and new data emanating from the project outcomes:

Key Partnerships:

- Collaboration with public and private entities for licensing agreements.
- Consortium partners jointly manage the development using open-source tools or their codebase.

Key Activities:

- Development and management of IWW simulators integrating climate scenarios and new project data.
- Licensing and customization of the software for various stakeholders.

Key Resources:

- The software engine and data that support investigations into the effects of climate change and natural hazards.
- Intellectual property developed within the consortium.

Value Propositions:

- Provides a holistic risk and resilience assessment for IWW infrastructure.
- Offers a unified assessment of impacts across interconnected IWW sites for all pertinent perils.
- Enables a unique common operational picture and incident management from a single integrated platform.

Customer Relationships:

- Customization services for each client and/or case study to ensure the software meets specific needs.
- Ongoing support and updates to the software as part of licensing agreements.

Channels:

- Direct sales to city managers, service providers, civil protection agencies, research institutes, and government bodies.
- Licensing agreements with public and private entities.

Customer Segments:

- City managers, service providers, civil protection agencies, research institutes, technological centers, universities, related EU-funded projects, government bodies, and policymakers.

Cost Structure:

- Development and maintenance costs of the IWW simulator.
- Costs associated with customization services for clients.
- Licensing and intellectual property management costs.

Revenue Streams:

- Licensing fees from public and private entities for the use of the software.
- Customization services for specific applications beyond the PLOTO pilot sites.
- Potential royalty-sharing agreements within the consortium for commercialization of the IWW simulator.

ER5: Multi-Hazard Vulnerability Modules and Assessment Toolkit for IWW.

Business model canvas for KER 5 Asset Physical Impact - Multi-Hazard Vulnerability Modules and Assessment Toolkit for IWW:

Key Partnerships:

- Collaboration between NTUA (National Technical University of Athens) and SORECC for co-development.
- Partnerships with public and private entities for licensing or royalty-sharing agreements.

Key Activities:

- Development of a standardized open format for coding Multi-Hazard Vulnerability Modules (MHVMs).
- Processing and exploiting MHVMs through software development.
- Development the exposure model with the assets per demonstration case; Define the hazard stressors associated with each site and asset; Analyze the response of the assets under the specific hazard stressors; Compute the vulnerability of the assets; Encode vulnerability in MHVM json data structure

Key Resources:

- Expertise in vulnerability assessment and toolkit development from NTUA and SORECC.
- Software for processing and exploiting MHVMs.
- Hazard stressors / characteristics of the assets/ importance of the assets

Value Propositions:

- Providing a comprehensive assessment of IWW infrastructure vulnerabilities through MHVMs.
- Enhancing interoperability of academic and industrial applications with a standardized coding format.
- Assess the impact of natural hazards on the assets of a region.
- Incorporation of multiple natural hazards.
- Exploitation of available asset data.
- Computationally frugal large-scale vulnerability assessment for IWW.
- Assisting the rehabilitation/emergency action planning.

Customer Relationships:

- Engagement with academic and industrial users through future research projects and licensing agreements.
- Dissemination of research findings and toolkits through public conferences and academic channels.
- The KER will be exploited through NTUA and SoReCC's communication and commercial channels (note: NTUA is an academic institution and SoReCC a non-profit organisation).

Services to be provided:

- Software-as-a-Service (SaaS), in which customers will purchase the toolkit for developing MHVMs on their own
- Tool support & maintenance services.

Channels:

- Licensing and royalty-sharing agreements for software exploitation.
- Academic publications, international conferences, and other established channels for dissemination.
- Co-operation with private companies and educational institutions, Own-channels

Customer Segments:

- Service providers, civil protection agencies, research institutes, technological centers, and universities.
- Entities involved in related EU-funded projects.
- Niche market: Public authorities, port operators, operations of infrastructure, academia

Cost Structure:

- Research and development costs for the vulnerability modules and assessment toolkit.
- Costs associated with collaboration, licensing, and dissemination activities.
- Start-up costs are calculated by estimating the number of Personnel Hours (PH) needed to develop and implement the component of the Business Plan (target TRL >= 8). No other costs are required.
- During development, testing and validation: $300 \text{ PH} * 42\text{€} = 12,600\text{€}$
 - Recurring expenses are calculated by estimating the number of Personnel Hours (PH) needed to develop and implement the component of the Business Plan. No other costs are required.
- After deployment:
 - Annual customer support expenses: $100 \text{ PH} * 32\text{€} = 3,200\text{€}$
 - Annual maintenance expenses: $100 \text{ PH} * 42\text{€} = 4,200\text{€}$
 - Marketing: 10% of the annual revenue for the 1st year - 5% of the annual revenue from the 3rd year and after

Revenue Streams:

- Revenue from licensing agreements with public and private entities.
- Potential revenue from consultancy and advisory services related to the application of MHVMs.
- Revenues are calculated by estimating the Average Revenue Per User (ARPU) as follows
Initialisation cost: 15,000€ – 20,000€.
- The initialisation cost depends the number of assets to be included and the requested level of analysis detail and the number of hazards, e.g., earthquake, flood, wind.
- Customisation fee (optional): $50 \text{ PH} * 150\text{€} = 7,500\text{€}$
The customization fee is related to the cost of integrating the module the risk assessment platform (if available) of the customer (integration to customer's legacy system), thus being optional.
Annual royalty fee: 3,000€
Expected number of customers:
1st year: 1 EU local port authority (either IWW or sea port)

- 2nd year: 1 EU local port authority
- 3rd year: 2 EU local port authorities, 1 US/global (either IWW or sea port)
- Other sources of revenues: Own budget, Angel investors, New EU-funded research projects

ER6: Common Operational Picture (COP) and Incident Management System (IMS), adapted to PLOTO needs and selected scenarios.

Business model canvas for KER 6 Decision Support System and Mission Control - Common Operational Picture (COP) and Incident Management System (IMS):

Key Partnerships:

- STWS [Leader], all technical partners, end-users
- Collaboration within the PLOTO consortium to pilot and deploy the solution.
- Potential partnerships with key players in the Waterway Transportation Software and Services Market.

Key Activities:

- Development and improvement of COP&IWAT solutions tailored to PLOTO requirements.
- Offering new and improved software solutions based on the integrated PLOTO platform's knowledge and components.
- The key activities involve developing tailored Common Operational Picture (COP) and Incident Management Systems (IMS) specific to PLOTO's needs. This includes integrating various data sources and communication channels to enhance decision-making and operational coordination in different scenarios.

Key Resources:

- Advanced COP&IWAT components integrated into product lines for converged security, smart mobility, and smart cities solutions.
- Expertise in end-to-end and enterprise-level solutions for the management of large and critical infrastructures.
- End users data, Technical providers data, Sensors data

Value Propositions:

- Providing comprehensive IWW infrastructure analysis to identify strengths, weaknesses, risks, and opportunities.
- Developing comprehensive risk mitigation planning and implementation actions.
- Offering ongoing support for the maintenance of IWW infrastructure.
- The value proposition here lies in offering a specialized Common Operational Picture and Incident Management System that is precisely tailored to the unique challenges and scenarios faced by inland waterway and public safety authorities. This system enhances operational coordination, improves decision-making during critical incidents, and ensures efficient resource management, thus directly contributing to heightened safety and security in challenging river environments.

Customer Relationships:

- Building relationships with IWW infrastructure operators through innovative and differentiated solutions.
- Addressing an unmet market need with COP&IWAT solutions.
- Customer relationships will be based on designing and implementing specific solutions that align with client requirements and specifications.

Channels:

- Direct sales to IWW infrastructure operators and integration into STWS product lines.
- Marketing and promotion through the PLOTO consortium's networks and industry events.

- The concept and system components are presented to public safety organizations, such as the Greek fire service, the General Secretariat of Civil Protection, and authorities with whom Satways has professional relations and contacts.

Customer Segments:

- IWW infrastructure operators as the primary customer segment.
- The customer segment for this system merges inland waterway authorities with public safety organizations and regional river-related authorities. This integrated group benefits from a system tailored for specific, high-impact scenarios along waterways, enhancing their capabilities in emergency management, coordination, and rapid response to incidents, thereby improving overall safety and operational efficiency in river environments.

Cost Structure:

- Research and development costs for creating and improving COP&IWAT solutions.
- Costs related to collaboration within the consortium and with potential market players.
- The financial feasibility of developing a business based on adapting COP and IMS to PLOTO requirements appears promising. The estimated one-time start-up costs range from €270,000 to €430,000, while recurring expenses are estimated at €25,000 to €40,000 per year. The project offers various revenue streams, including customized service fees, subscription models, partnership and collaboration revenue, and training and consultation services. These revenue streams, combined with the estimated expenses, suggest a viable business opportunity with the potential to achieve profitability. The specific revenue generation will depend on market demand, pricing strategies, and strategic partnerships.

Revenue Streams:

- Sales of new and improved software solutions to IWW infrastructure operators.
- Potential revenue from joint exploitation with consortium partners or through individual efforts by STWS.
- The first revenue stream is Customized Service Fees where clients are charged for personalized solutions. Another important source of revenue is Subscription Models, which offers regular income through subscriptions for system access. The project can also earn revenue through Partnership and Collaboration by leveraging collaborations with other entities. Lastly, Training and Consultation Services can provide additional income by capitalizing on the need for expert guidance and user training. These combined revenue sources, along with the project's expenses and market strategy, suggest a strong potential for profitability.

ER13: River Digital Twin

Business model canvas for KER 13 ML models for the Development of the Digital Twins (DT):

Key Partnerships:

- Collaboration with port operators, shipping companies, logistics providers, government agencies, environmental organizations, advocacy groups, and academic and research institutions involved in port operation, management, and regulation.
- Partnerships with technology providers for sensors, computational resources, and data analysis.

Key Activities:

- Development and maintenance of ML-based algorithms for digital twins.
- Real-time monitoring and predictive maintenance using data collected from sensors and historical environmental data.

Key Resources:

- AI and ML algorithms developed by EXUS AI Labs.

- Digital twin technology for real-time monitoring and predictive analysis.

Value Propositions:

- Improved safety and reduced downtime through real-time monitoring of navigability parameters.
- Increased efficiency in vessel routing, cargo handling, and port operations.
- Predictive maintenance to identify potential issues, allowing proactive repairs.
- Risk management by simulating scenarios to understand and manage environmental risks.
- Environmental monitoring to take proactive measures for environmental protection.

Customer Relationships:

- After-sales support and continuous updates for the digital twin system.
- Customization of digital twin solutions to meet specific customer requirements.

Channels:

- Direct sales to port operators and related stakeholders.
- Integration of ML algorithms into EXUS's existing product portfolio for wider application.

Customer Segments:

- Port operators, shipping companies, logistics providers, government agencies, and others involved in port operations and management.

Cost Structure:

- Development and operational costs of digital twin technology and ML algorithms.
- Investment in sensors, computational resources, and data analysis tools.

Revenue Streams:

- Software selling through licensing agreements.
- Revenue from consulting and customization services for digital twin implementation